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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Description
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
CSO	Citizen Science Organisations
DI	Data Infrastructures
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EFC	EOSC FAIR Champions
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IIS	Individuals in Science
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NLI	National Level Initiatives
NOAD	National Open Access Desk
NOSCI	National Open Science Cloud Initiative
NFDI	Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (National Research Data Infrastructure in Germany)
ORE	Open Research Europe
PO	Policymaking Organisations
PUB	Publishers
RI	Research Infrastructures
RFO	Research Funding Organisations
RPO	Research Performing Organisations
RoP	Rules of Participation
SF	Synchronisation Force
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda of the EOSC
SS&A	Scientific Societies & Academies
TBT	Technical Bridging Team
TFIR	Turning FAIR into Reality
UVP	Unique Value Proposition
UX	User Experience
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

Over the past three years, Work Package 7 (WP7) "Dissemination, exploitation and communication" has driven comprehensive project outreach across all levels. The team collaborated through a constant dialogue with the other Work Packages, to effectively address stakeholders and foster their engagement throughout the project lifecycle, in order to ensure the FAIR-IMPACT objectives and impacts are achieved. This deliverable represents the final outcomes in terms of dissemination, exploitation and communication as defined and reported in earlier outputs of the FAIR-IMPACT projects, i.e. *D7.1 Dissemination, exploitation and communication plan*,¹ *M7.2 review of D7.1 Dissemination Exploitation Communication Plan (Ver1.1)*,² and *M7.4 - Impact Report [D&E&C results preliminary version]*.³ Within this final report, the accomplished objectives, implemented activities and results are detailed along the sections below:

- **Section 1:** Introduces the variety of implemented activities in the context of the FAIR-IMPACT project;
- **Section 2:** Briefly describes the stakeholder groups and the impact achieved;
- **Section 3:** Reports on the results of the specific support programmes developed in order to incentivise the uptake of FAIR-enabling practices;
- **Section 4:** Describes and lists the Implementation stories that have been realised from the organisations supported by the FAIR-IMPACT project; they are grouped under the kind of support received and related scientific domain;
- **Section 5:** Provides an overview of the real-life use cases produced and published;
- **Section 6:** Gives the view on the FAIR Implementation Framework and the resulting catalogue of resources;
- **Section 7:** Highlights the impactful Synchronisation Force Workshops series and their key outcomes, presenting recommendations that emerged and the discussions;
- **Section 8:** Reports on the contribution provided by the 13 EOSC FAIR Champions;
- **Section 9:** Reports the many events that FAIR-IMPACT organised and the participation to third party ones;
- **Section 10:** Provides the list of the peer-reviewed publications and scientific papers produced by the partners (in addition to documents and deliverables);
- **Section 11:** Describes all the digital/Online/Offline Communication activities performed by the WP7 and the other WPs in order to properly deliver the message to the stakeholders, including outcomes and conclusions.

¹ Pittonet, S., Davidson, J., Meneses, R., Mari, M., O'Connor, R., Nordling, J., Aubin, S., Kalaitzi, V., Grootveld, M., Turner, D., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., Horton, L., Whyte, A., Marjamaa-Mankinen, L., Mejias, G., & Dillo, I. (2024). D7.1 - Dissemination, exploitation and communication plan (V1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10785484>

² Pittonet, S., Davidson, J., Meneses, R., Mari, M., O'Connor, R., Kalaitzi, V., Grootveld, M., Turner, D., & Marjamaa-Mankinen, L. (2023). M7.2 review of D7.1 Dissemination Exploitation Communication Plan (Ver1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7995246>

³ Pittonet Gaiarin, S. (2024). M7.4 - Impact Report [D&E&C results preliminary version] (v1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11544863>

This report describes in detail activities performed for the communication and dissemination of the project's work and outputs, as well as activities towards the exploitation and sustainability of its results, e.g. through synchronisation efforts and recommendations, in line with relevant recent publications of the project, such as the FAIR adoption pathway white paper,⁴ the Recommendations for a FAIR EOSC - White Paper of the FAIR-IMPACT Synchronisation Force,⁵ and the upcoming Sustainability plan.⁶

⁴ Davidson, J., Newbold, E., Verburg, M., Thorpe, D. E., Linés, C., & Mari, M. (2025). D7.2 - FAIR adoption pathway white paper (1.0 Draft not yet approved by the European Commission). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15210109>

⁵ Grootveld, M., Fink, A. S., Jonquet, C., González Guardia, E., Dillo, I., Nordling, J., Davidson, J., Marjamaa-Mankinen, L., Verburg, M., Priddy, M., GRAU, N., & Pittonet Gaiarin, S. (2025). D1.3 Recommendations for a FAIR EOSC - White Paper of the FAIR-IMPACT Synchronisation Force (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14979705>

⁶ To be published by end of May 2025.

1. Introduction

FAIR-IMPACT WP7 is in charge of ensuring that the dissemination, exploitation and communication activities of all FAIR-IMPACT WPs is done smoothly through multiple modalities, to properly promote project results to the key targeted stakeholders.

The impact achieved thanks to the variety of activities implemented in the context of the FAIR-IMPACT project is remarkable. Dissemination had been capillary spread across stakeholders, organisations and individuals in Europe (and beyond). This document provides an overview of the dissemination, communication and exploitation key channels exploited and the results in terms of engagement achieved.

The overall FAIR-IMPACT community members, registered on the FAIR-IMPACT website, shows active participation from different countries in Europe, and also interest from outside the European territories. More than 3600⁷ users, representing more than 90 countries, have registered on the FAIR-IMPACT website. They are subscribers of the project events, open-call applicants and/or webinar/workshops participants.

Figure 1: country of origin of FAIR-IMPACT registered users

When asked to confirm which stakeholder categories they belong to, in the majority of the cases users gave multiple answers, identifying with more than one of the stakeholder

⁷ 3615 as of April 2025

categories defined by the FAIR-IMPACT project. The figure below presents the overview of the stakeholder categories represented:

Figure 2: types of organisation represented in the FAIR-IMPACT community, as declared by registered users

All the stakeholder categories have been the target of more than one project activity, and the outcomes are presented extensively in the following chapters.

2. Stakeholder Engagement & Impact achieved

2.1. National Level Initiatives

The National Level Initiatives were one of the three key stakeholder categories that received expert (non financial) support. The first round of support⁸ was provided between 30th August and 1st November 2023. After this first round and an assessment of the process and support provided, the project team decided to update the process by partnering with EOSC mandated organisations, where possible, into providing a separate strand for National Level Initiatives through the second round⁹ of expert (non-financial) support between September 2024 and January 2025.

A total of 17 workshops and peer exchange sessions were held between January 2024 and January 2025 targeting Research Infrastructures, EOSC Mandated Organisations, Thematic National Initiatives on FAIR and National Repositories. 25 speakers were mobilised to give advice on how to implement the FAIR principles at national level. In terms of participation, about 75 individuals were involved, representing 38 different organisations from 20 different countries.

The support was broad because at national level there are many ways of influencing the implementation of the FAIR principles. It also depends on the scope of each organisation, which can vary from policy to funding. The programmes allowed the organisation to learn from the different perspectives available to them and to focus on those that were most

⁸ <https://fair-impact.eu/2nd-open-call-support-opens-30-august>

⁹ <https://fair-impact.eu/second-call-national-level-initiatives>

relevant. In the end, the participants had benefited from specific mentoring sessions, exchanges with peers from their country and inspiring examples from the speakers.

Most of the participants produced an action plan for the implementation of FAIR in their perimeter, planning the interdependencies of each action and prioritising their objectives. They learned from each other and identified who in their country and at European level could be an ally in working towards the FAIR principles.

Finally, based on this experience and the presentations given by the speakers, the FAIR-IMPACT group working on the NLI programme (Task 2.5 - Engaging and supporting adoption at national level) developed a web page on the FAIR-IMPACT website¹⁰ (which will continue to be accessible for 5 years after the end of the project). The web page collects information for national initiatives for FAIR, so that they can still benefit from the experience of the programme. The page lists the 38 NLI that joined the support programme, from 20 different countries.

2.2 Research Performing Organisations & Research Communities & Infrastructures

Research Performing Organisations (RPOs), i.e. Research institutes and Universities have been the target of several activities. Out of the 3600+ registered users on the FAIR-IMPACT website, more than 2000 recognised themselves as RPOs. One of these activities was a programme providing expert (non-financial) support for RPOs,¹¹ which ran between February and October 2024.

20 individuals representatives of RPOs have been successfully engaged in this expert (non-financial) RPO specific support programme and received support to better understand the drivers for becoming more FAIR-enabling, to assess their current FAIR-enabling capacity and develop plans for improvement and engagement within their institutes.¹² 10 workshops were organised for them including mentors from the FAIR-IMPACT project. A total of 13 FAIR Implementation stories targeting RPOs have been written as a result of the support received, 6 of which are published on Zenodo at the time of writing, another 7 will be uploaded by June.¹³

2.3 Repositories and Data Service Providers

This stakeholder category includes (meta) data /PID and other relevant service providers, as well as repositories. There were two open calls for expert (non-financial) support offered

¹⁰ <https://fair-impact.eu/national-level-initiatives-fair-implementation>

¹¹ <https://fair-impact.eu/2nd-open-call-support-opens-30-august>

¹² <https://fair-impact.eu/2nd-open-call-support-opens-30-august>

¹³ See

https://fair-impact.eu/implementation-adoption-stories?field_support_received_target_id%5B106%5D=106

for Repositories and Data Service Providers (first call¹⁴ and second call¹⁵), resulting in the programme being run twice. Selected participants received dedicated workshops, curated support tools, and the peer-to-peer support of two mentors throughout the programme duration. A total of 15 organisations were supported through these activities in creating their FAIR Implementation Action Plan, and shared their experiences in FAIR Implementation Stories. A total of eleven FAIR Implementation Workshops were also organised for this specific stakeholder group, which were open for anyone to join. These workshops covered topics deemed relevant for Repositories and Data Service Providers, such as the newly released version of the OAIS framework or the FAIRification of sensitive data.

One example of financial support was specifically offered to PID service providers, PID managers, and data repository providers.¹⁶ The support action, Creating EOSC-compliant Persistent Identifier (PID) policies, encouraged participating organisations to complete self-assessments of their PID policies using the Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT) developed by the FAIRCORE4EOSC project.¹⁷ Rather than focusing on specific PID types, the support action offered general best practice guidelines to create and assess PID policies. 12 organisations were supported during the program through workshops and bi-weekly office hours. They gave valuable input for the development of the CAT tool and PID policy requirements and other valuable feedback in the FAIR implementation stories they created. Participants gained knowledge on current PID practices and approaches different institutions use, expectations set out by the EOSC PID Policy, the overall PID ecosystem, their maturity concerning PID management, and their areas for improvement. During the support program they started to focus more on policy work, termination procedures, quality control, metadata management and resolvability and long-term sustainability of PIDs.

Two more examples specifically targeting repositories were part of the second¹⁸ and third¹⁹ call for financial support: Recommendations for trustworthy and FAIR-enabling data repositories²⁰ and Testing the trustworthy and FAIR-enabling repositories prototype.²¹ These two support actions followed up from one another, supporting repositories in evaluating how well their organization was already exposing important information, and subsequently improving this through the guidelines and prototypes developed in Task 5.4. Across the two support actions, 15 participating organisations worked to improve their information exposure to better showcase their trustworthiness through transparency. The participants also provided valuable feedback for the support team to take into account the further development of the guidelines and the prototypes. Support efforts such as these

¹⁴ <https://fair-impact.eu/2nd-open-call-support-opens-30-august>

¹⁵ <https://fair-impact.eu/2nd-open-call-route-1-expert-non-financial-support-open>

¹⁶ <https://fair-impact.eu/support-offer-2-creating-eosc-compliant-persistent-identifier-pid-policies>

¹⁷ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/>

¹⁸ <https://fair-impact.eu/2nd-open-call-route-2-support>

¹⁹ <https://fair-impact.eu/3rd-open-call-route-2-support-opens-30-sept>

²⁰ <https://fair-impact.eu/support-offer-3-recommendations-trustworthy-and-fair-enabling-data-repositories>

²¹ <https://fair-impact.eu/testing-tdr-and-fair-enabling-prototype>

ones allowed repositories and data service providers to pick and choose different topics and skills to improve and learn more about, also at different levels of expertise.

2.4 Policy Makers & Research Funding Organisations

FAIR-IMPACT directly contributes through its activities and outputs to key action areas of the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda on identifiers, metadata and ontologies, FAIR metrics and certification, interoperability, rules of participation, landscape monitoring and communication. Throughout the three years of its implementation, the project as a whole and its individual work packages and partners have established and maintained open channels with policy makers and research funding organisations at national, European and institutional levels. Starting with its direct funder, the European Commission, and the main relevant policy stakeholder that is the EOSC Association (EOSC-A), FAIR-IMPACT has participated in all relevant activities, either at key events (e.g. EOSC Symposium and Tripartite events) but also at targeted discussions, such as the Horizon Europe INFRAEOSC project concertation meetings and the EOSC Winter School in 2024²² and 2025.²³ Representatives of the project have not only actively participated, but have also contributed to the co-organisation of sessions, as well as by initiating discussions on critical topics, e.g. on the sustainability of project results and their validation and uptake by the EOSC community. Furthermore, several project partners participate in the EOSC Forum, relevant working groups and EOSC Task Forces, while the project has directly contributed and/or responded to Task Force papers, e.g. through its response to "DRAFT: Developing and implementing the semantic interoperability recommendations of the EOSC Interoperability Framework",²⁴ response to "FAIR Assessment Tools: Towards an "Apples to Apples" Comparisons",²⁵ and response to "Community-driven governance of FAIRness assessment: an open issue, an open discussion".²⁶

FAIR-IMPACT engaged with policy makers and national research funding organisations also at national level with its activities, e.g. through its National Roadshows that have been, in the majority, co-organised with the local EOSC mandated organisations, to ensure relevance for key players at national level and targeted promotion. The following representatives of Ministries and governmental agencies have joined as speakers at National Roadshows:

²² <https://eosc.eu/eosc-focus-project/winter-school-2024/>

²³ <https://eosc.eu/events/eosc-winter-school-2025/>

²⁴ Jonquet, C., Gonzalez, E., Aubin, S., & Grau, N. (2024). FAIR-IMPACT project response to "DRAFT: Developing and implementing the semantic interoperability recommendations of the EOSC Interoperability Framework" (Version V1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10874897>

²⁵ Maaïke Verburg, Robert Huber, Clement Jonquet, & Daniel Garijo. (2023). FAIR-IMPACT project response to "FAIR Assessment Tools: Towards an "Apples to Apples" Comparisons" (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7848102>

²⁶ Maaïke Verburg, Mike Priddy, Robert Huber, Clement Jonquet, Neil Chue Hong, Daniel Garijo, Xenia Kechagioglou, Joy Davidson, Ingrid Dillo, & Vasso Kalaitzi. (2023). FAIR-IMPACT project response to "Community-driven governance of FAIRness assessment: an open issue, an open discussion" (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7848127>

- **Ivan Skubic**, Scientific Advisor, Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of **Slovenia**
- **York Sure-Vetter**, Director of NFDI, **German** National Research Data Infrastructure
- **Janne Pölonen**, Federation of **Finnish** Learned Societies
- **Jenny O'Neill**, Research Engagement Officer at HEAnet - **Ireland's** National Research & Education Network

FAIR-IMPACT has so far published two policy briefs, one in 2023²⁷ and a second in 2024,²⁸ describing the project's contributions and interactions with regards to the EOSC SRIA. A third and final policy brief is expected in 2025 as part of the project's final reporting.

2.5 EOSC Community

FAIR-IMPACT has dedicated significant resources in synchronising with the EOSC and FAIR ecosystems by establishing a specific mechanism for this purpose, the Synchronisation Force.²⁹ Building on the successful Synchronisation Force series³⁰ of the FAIRsFAIR project, FAIR-IMPACT has organised three Synchronisation Force Workshops (in 2022,³¹ 2023³² and 2024³³). Each provided dedicated sessions across key topics reflecting the work of the project on Metrics and FAIR Assessment, Persistent Identifiers, Legal & Organisational Interoperability, Trustworthy and FAIR-enabling repositories, Metadata, semantics and Interoperability, and Sustainability of project outputs. Representatives from the FAIR and EOSC ecosystem were invited to actively contribute to the online sessions of each edition of the Synchronisation Force Workshop. The results from the three reports led to the creation of a White Paper for Synchronisation,³⁴ mapped to two Strategic Pillars of the EOSC

²⁷ Kalaitzi, V., Dillo, I., Turner, D., Ashley, K., Davidson, J., Nordling, J., Parland-von Essen, J., Jonquet, C., Aubin, S., Priddy, M., Verburg, M., Fink, A. S., Rouchon, O., Pittonet, S., Mari, M., & Meneses, R. (2023). EOSC Policy Brief for FAIR-IMPACT. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8255645>

²⁸ Kalaitzi, V., Dillo, I., Ashley, K., Davidson, J., Nordling, J., Jonquet, C., Aubin, S., Priddy, M., Verburg, M., Fink, A. S., Rouchon, O., Pittonet, S., Mari, M., Meneses, R., & de Leeuw, L. (2024). FAIR-IMPACT EOSC Policy Brief for FAIR-IMPACT_V2.0. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13348297>

²⁹ <https://fair-impact.eu/synchronisation-force>

³⁰ <https://fair-impact.eu/fairsfair-legacy>

³¹ Grootveld, M., Pittonet Gaiarin, S., Davidson, J., Dillo, I., O'Connor, R., Marjamaa-Mankinen, L., Verburg, M., & Jonquet, C. (2023). M1.7 - First synchronisation workshop. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7692063>

³² Grootveld, M., Pittonet Gaiarin, S., Davidson, J., Dillo, I., Verburg, M., Rouchon, O., Priddy, M., Nordling, J., Marjamaa-Mankinen, L., Gonzalez, E., Fink Kjeldgaard, A.-S., David, R., & Dennis, R. (2024). M1.8 - Second synchronisation workshop. Synchronisation Force 2nd Workshop - November 2023. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11082238>

³³ Everhardt, M., Fink, A. S., Jonquet, C., Gonzalez, E., Dillo, I., Nordling, J., Davidson, J., Horton, L., Marjamaa-Mankinen, L., Verburg, M., Priddy, M., GRAU, N., Rouchon, O., & Pittonet Gaiarin, S. (2025). M1.9 Third Synchronisation Workshop Report - 20250211_Graphical version. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14848907>

³⁴ Grootveld, M., Fink, A. S., Jonquet, C., González Guardia, E., Dillo, I., Nordling, J., Davidson, J., Marjamaa-Mankinen, L., Verburg, M., Priddy, M., GRAU, N., & Pittonet Gaiarin, S. (2025). D1.3 Recommendations for a FAIR EOSC - White Paper of the FAIR-IMPACT Synchronisation Force (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14979705>

Multi-Annual Roadmap 2026-2027 and the relevant Task Forces and Opportunity Area Expert Groups under the EOSC Association, to facilitate their uptake and impact.

Furthermore, the FAIR-IMPACT project worked closely with several INFRAEOSC projects,³⁵ not only through its participation in the Horizon Europe projects concertation meetings organised by the European Commission and the EOSC-A, but also through collaboration plans and shared activities (e.g. with FAIRCORE4EOSC, Skills4EOSC, FAIR-EASE and HORIZON-ZEN), while it has also exchanged input with BY-COVID, EOSC4Cancer, WorldFAIR and OSCARS through shared partners. Further collaboration has taken place through the co-organisation of events (e.g. RDA, EUDAT, see sections below), as well as through the project's input in the EOSC macro roadmap.³⁶

FAIR-IMPACT has also been the initiator of sustainability discussions with the EOSC-A in October 2024, with the participation of Skills4EOSC, FAIRCORE4EOSC, FAIR EASE, RDA TIGER and RAISE. Furthermore, representatives of FAIR-IMPACT participated in the FIDELIS & EOSC EDEN³⁷ kick-off meeting in February 2025 also with an eye on sustainability and further steps in relation to FAIR-IMPACT outputs and recommendations that are relevant for long-term preservation and the community of existing and emerging Trustworthy Digital Repositories.

2.6 The collaboration with FAIRCORE4EOSC

The FAIR-IMPACT and FAIRCORE4EOSC projects have been collaborating by design. They had the mandate to work together from the funding calls they responded to, hence they started their collaboration by leveraging synergies and working hand-in-hand right from their (common) start date. A Technical Bridging Team³⁸ (TBT) was established to ensure technical alignment between the two projects, as well as other initiatives, such as the HE Technology Group. A collaboration plan was established as an internal, living document between the projects to define collaboration areas across their activities. The two projects co-organised their kick-off meeting³⁹ and FAIRfest⁴⁰ (closing event), as well as several sessions in third party events, and contributed to each-other's internal meetings (e.g. FAIR-IMPACT annual All-Hands meetings and FAIRCORE4EOSC technical meetings) (More information available on chapter 9 below). The FAIRCORE4EOSC project provided three tools (the Data Type Registry, Vocabulary Service, and Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry) as support offers⁴¹ under the FAIR-IMPACT financial support programme, collaborated on the FAIR implementation workshop on Semantic Artefact Mappings and provided components for the FAIR Implementation Catalogue, namely CAT⁴², EOSC Data Type Registry, Metadata and Schema Crosswalk Registry (MSCR), EOSC PID Graph, EOSC PID

³⁵ Projects funded under Horizon Europe Research Infrastructures contributing to the implementation of the European Open Science Cloud.

³⁶ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-macro-roadmap/>

³⁷ <https://eden-fidelis.eu/>

³⁸ <https://fair-impact.eu/technical-bridging-team>

³⁹ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fairimpact-events/fair-impact-kick-meeting>

⁴⁰ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/fairfest-celebrating-advancements-fair-solutions-eosc>

⁴¹ <https://fair-impact.eu/managing-data-schemas-vocabularies>

⁴² <https://catalogue.fair-impact.eu/resources/cat>

Meta Resolver (PIDMR), Research Activity Identifier Service (RAiD), EOSC Research Discovery Graph Service (RDGraph), EOSC Research Software APIs and Connectors (RSAC) and the EOSC Software Heritage Mirror.

3. Support programme engagement and updated results

3.1. Expert (non financial) support (Route 1)

Successful applicants to the open calls to join the FAIR-IMPACT support programmes worked with FAIR-IMPACT mentors/project partners and, in some cases, external experts to learn how to support the uptake of FAIR-enabling practices. The programmes included participation in a series of virtual workshops based on the FAIR Implementation Framework, independent homework, and one-to-one support. These programmes were aimed at those who are just getting started with supporting the FAIR Principles or are less advanced on their FAIR-enabling journey.

Three support programmes were developed:

- 1st call for expert (non-financial support)⁴³
 - for RPOs (February - October 2024)
 - for Repositories and Data Service Providers (January - September 2024)
 - for National Level Initiatives (February - September 2024)
- 2nd call for expert (non) financial support:
 - for Repositories and Data Service Providers⁴⁴ (September 2024 - March 2025)
 - for National Level Initiatives⁴⁵ (September 2024 - January 2025)

Participation in these expert (non-financial) support programmes aimed to help the different stakeholder groups to better understand the drivers for becoming more FAIR-enabling, to self-assess their current FAIR-enabling capacity and develop plans for improvement, and to ensure that they have an effective engagement strategy in place to facilitate uptake. The structure of the programmes is based around the FAIR Implementation Framework stages (See chapter 6). During the support programme, participants attended a series of 7-10 virtual workshops (depending on the support programme) where FAIR-IMPACT mentors and external experts introduced participants to key concepts and approaches. A key feature of the support programme was mentoring. Each successful applicant met with a pair of FAIR-IMPACT mentors at least monthly to help them assess their current FAIR-enabling capacity and to plan for improvements. Enabling knowledge exchange was one of the key objectives of the support programmes. To this end, each allocated two workshops during which participants shared their experiences with their peers.

⁴³ <https://fair-impact.eu/2nd-open-call-support-opens-30-august>

⁴⁴ <https://fair-impact.eu/2nd-open-call-route-1-expert-non-financial-support-open>

⁴⁵ <https://fair-impact.eu/second-call-national-level-initiatives>

Figure 3: overall figures of the FAIR-IMPACT expert (non-financial) support programme

Examples of the feedback received:

- “I especially appreciated when speakers shared tips, ‘small’ things which could be implemented relatively easily.”
- “Personal consultations and discussions based on the situation in [my] institution and [my] country.”
- “I really appreciated the specific practical exercises, which allowed me to reflect and explore with colleagues the strengths and areas for improvement.”

3.2. Financial support through cascading grants (Route 2)

This route provided defined support actions where guidance and assistance were provided to implement and test one or more tools and approaches. Successful applicants received financial support through the project’s cascading grants to enable their participation in a series of virtual, hands-on workshops. This support was aimed at those who are more advanced on their FAIR-enabling journey and ready to test specific tools and approaches. The first open call⁴⁶ for financial support was launched at the end of March 2023. The second⁴⁷ open call launched at the end of January 2024. The third open call for financial support launched in October 2024.⁴⁸ The open calls invited applications to join one or more of twelve defined support actions over the life of the FAIR-IMPACT project.

Support actions included:

- FAIRness assessment challenge⁴⁹
- Enabling FAIR Signposting and RO-Crate for content/metadata discovery and consumption⁵⁰

⁴⁶ <https://fair-impact.eu/1st-open-call-route-2-support-closed>

⁴⁷ <https://fair-impact.eu/2nd-open-call-route-2-support>

⁴⁸ <https://fair-impact.eu/3rd-open-call-route-2-support-opens-30-sept>

⁴⁹ <https://fair-impact.eu/support-offer-1-fairness-assessment-challenge-datasets-and-semantic-artefacts>

⁵⁰ <https://fair-impact.eu/support-offer-2-enabling-fair-signposting-and-ro-crate-contentmetadata-discovery-and-consumption>

- Creating EOSC compliant PID policies⁵¹
- Assessing and improving research software⁵² using a new extension of F-UJI and by implementing the Research Software MetaData (RSMD) guidelines
- Recommendations for trustworthy and FAIR-enabling repositories⁵³
- Improving the availability and machine readability of data policies⁵⁴
- Managing data types, schemas and vocabularies and crosswalks for FAIR researcher related metadata⁵⁵
- Creating EOSC compliant interoperability policies based on EOSC Interoperability Framework (IF)⁵⁶
- Testing the trustworthy and FAIR-enabling repositories prototype⁵⁷
- Implementation of a shared API for semantic catalogues⁵⁸
- Review of FC4E metadata types recordings

Figure 4: overall figures of the financial support programme

Examples of the feedback received from participants:

- *“It was a very nice experience and the results will be undoubtedly useful for my organisation and for me.”*
- *“I really like the way you support science and pave the way for it.”*
- *“You get better by participating in communities. You don’t get better on your own.”*

⁵¹ <https://fair-impact.eu/support-offer-2-creating-eosc-compliant-persistent-identifier-pid-policies>

⁵² <https://fair-impact.eu/support-offer-1-assessment-and-improvement-research-software>

⁵³ <https://fair-impact.eu/support-offer-3-recommendations-trustworthy-and-fair-enabling-data-repositories>

⁵⁴ <https://fair-impact.eu/support-offer-4-improving-availability-and-machine-readability-data-policies-fairsharing>

⁵⁵ <https://fair-impact.eu/managing-data-schemas-vocabularies>

⁵⁶ <https://fair-impact.eu/creating-eosc-compliant-interoperability-policies>

⁵⁷ <https://fair-impact.eu/testing-trustworthy-and-fair-enabling-prototype>

⁵⁸ <https://fair-impact.eu/implementing-shared-api-for-semantic-catalogues>

3.3. FAIR Implementation workshops (Route 3)

FAIR-IMPACT launched a series of free FAIR Implementation Workshops to help Research performing Organisations, Repositories & Data Service Providers and National Level Initiatives, in becoming familiar with FAIR-enabling tools, approaches and methods. The FAIR Implementation Workshop series⁵⁹ aimed to help our key stakeholders in Europe and globally to become familiar with FAIR-enabling tools, approaches, and methods. These openly available workshops were used to provide support to a broader cohort of stakeholders, expanding further than the key stakeholder groups addressed in the financial and expert (non-financial) support programmes. The project used these workshops to engage with its wider stakeholder base on FAIR-enabling tools, approaches and examples of good practice.

Figure 5: example of a banner of one of the FAIR Implementation Workshops, and figures on the workshops delivered and registrants

Each one of the 21 workshops, sometimes organised in cooperation with other initiatives from open science and communities, provided an overview of a specific FAIR-enabling activity, shared information on recent developments both from within FAIR-IMPACT and other initiatives as well as offered examples of good practices, practical tips and recommendations.

The workshop which reached the highest number of registrations (305) was the one focused on the Open Archival Information System (OAIS), an essential system to organise long term preservation at digital repositories. Other popular ones were focused on trustworthy repositories, the F-UJI to assess data FAIRness, costs and incentives of data management, FAIR practices in sensitive data, as well as the qualities, roles, and

⁵⁹ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-implementation-workshops>

responsibilities of a 'data champion'. The full list of workshops with registered numbers are provided in Annex 2.

4. FAIR Implementation stories

The FAIR Implementation Stories describe the experiences of the participants in the FAIR-IMPACT support programmes in real-life applications of FAIR Principles.

As presented in sections above, over the past three years the FAIR-IMPACT project provided practical advice and guidance on key FAIR-enabling topics, with best practices guidelines, critical assessment of the FAIRness of software/services/tools and fostering knowledge exchange between peers. As a result, almost 150 FAIR implementation stories were produced, as ideal tools for the participants in the support programmes to promote their work and progress in-line with their experience in receiving support from the project. Each implementation story showcases a specific intervention where participants received support from our project team to address challenges in implementing FAIR principles.

The stories were collected and curated in the form of narrative stories, emphasise the impacts achieved and are intended to share some of the lessons learned and examples of good practices that have been gained through participation in the FAIR-IMPACT support actions and support programmes.

Gathered in a specific section of the FAIR-IMPACT website⁶⁰, the FAIR Implementation and Adoption Stories have been linked to specific key topics (**Interoperability, Metadata & Ontologies, Metrics, Certification and Guidelines, PIDs**), **the support received** and the **FAIR Implementation Tools** used.

Each story has indicated the authors/editors list and the affiliations that participated. They include the **challenges encountered and addressed**, the **approach taken** in the process, and the actual **impact** reached with the support received.

The FAIR implementation stories are about 150, openly accessible and uploaded to the ZENODO project community.⁶¹

⁶⁰ <https://fair-impact.eu/implementation-adoption-stories>

⁶¹ At the time of writing 48 stories are published on Zenodo, 27 are ready to be published, another 70 will be finalised by and uploaded by June 2025
<https://zenodo.org/communities/fair-impact/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Figure 6: preview of the FAIR-Implementation stories page on the FAIR-IMPACT website

Figure 7: Implementation Stories - example of a cover of a downloadable version on ZENODO

5. FAIR Use-Cases

A specific section on the FAIR-IMPACT is dedicated to the experiences of the project's domain-specific integrated use case partners, i.e. project partners operating under a specific domain and contributing to the project with this characteristic, providing expertise and experience. This section includes detailed real-life "FAIR Use Cases"⁶² that showcase practical FAIR implementation examples with domain-specific characteristics that can be reuse from their own domain or even serve as examples of knowledge and practice exchange across domains. These stories are available as downloadable resources via the FAIR-IMPACT Community on Zenodo⁶³ and promoted across FAIR-IMPACT communication channels. The Use case leading partners demonstrated how FAIR principles can be successfully applied in different research contexts, providing valuable models that other researchers and institutions can adapt and implement.

They span diverse research areas across the scientific landscape.

Collected and featured in a comprehensive Booklet⁶⁴ under the project's distinctive branding, openly accessible from the ZENODO platform, each one identifies the key topic and the respective scientific domain:

- Earth and environmental sciences
- Ecology and biodiversity domain
- Life science
- Photon & Neutron science
- Social Sciences and Humanities
- Physical and Technical Sciences
- Archaeology

⁶² <https://fair-impact.eu/use-cases>

⁶³ <https://zenodo.org/communities/fair-impact/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

⁶⁴ https://fair-impact.eu/sites/default/files/2025-02/UseCases_Stories_A4_February2025.pdf

Figure 8 - Use cases Booklet cover

6. FAIR Implementation Framework

The FAIR Implementation Framework (FIF) consists of seven components (including the catalogue of resources) and is intended to help our key stakeholders to consider the bigger picture when it comes to enabling FAIR. The overall structure of the three support programmes described in chapter 3 was based around the stages outlined in the FAIR Implementation Framework⁶⁵, as in figure below.

⁶⁵ FAIR Implementation Framework <https://fair-impact.eu/fair-implementation-framework>

Figure 9: FAIR Implementation Framework

One of the components of the framework is a catalogue or resources (related to step 6 Implementing specific tools, methods and approaches) which is a browsable online tool which users can use to identify the tools/solutions most appropriate for different use cases. Desk research was carried out to identify a set of 60+ candidate resources for inclusion in the first iteration of the FIF catalogue of resources⁶⁶. These are presented in the annex of D2.1 Targeted landscape analysis report⁶⁷. The framework’s catalogue of resources was updated periodically to ensure that emerging approaches, tools and resources such as those resulting from ongoing related projects and initiatives were included. Over the past year, the FIF metadata was updated too, to include FAIR-IMPACT’s four thematic areas - Interoperability, Metadata & Semantics, Metrics & Assessment, and PIDs and facilitate search and filtering. In March 2025, FAIR-IMPACT undertook a review of the resources presented in the FIF catalogue to ensure that they were still accessible and that the emerging tools/approaches/solutions that were offered for testing and uptake via FAIR-IMPACT’s second⁶⁸ and third⁶⁹ open calls for financial support were included in the catalogue, including the components resulting from the FAIRCORE4EOSC project. By the

⁶⁶ <https://catalogue.fair-impact.eu/>

⁶⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/10785827>

⁶⁸ FAIR-IMPACT’s second open call for financial support <https://fair-impact.eu/2nd-open-call-route-2-support>

⁶⁹ FAIR-IMPACT’s third open call for financial support <https://fair-impact.eu/3rd-open-call-route-2-support-opens-30-sept>

end of the FAIR-IMPACT project, the FIF catalogue of resources included 53 tools/approaches/solutions⁷⁰.

Figure 10: FAIR Implementation Framework Catalogue of Resources

The catalogue and its resources were promoted via FAIR-IMPACT Newsletters and social media channels. The catalogue will remain online for 5 years after the project's conclusion. In order to boost visibility and help with sustainability, a record for the catalogue was also created on FAIRsharing⁷¹, the curated, informative and educational resource on data and metadata standards, inter-related to databases and data policies provided by the University of Oxford (which is also one of the resources listed in the FIF catalogue).

7. The FAIR-IMPACT Synchronisation Force and its legacy

Over the course of the project the Synchronisation Force organised three online synchronisation workshop series⁷² bringing together FAIR and EOSC ecosystem projects, infrastructures, and initiatives in Europe to assess the progress of work related to FAIR-IMPACT focus areas and EOSC SRIA⁷³ objectives. Inspired by strategic reports on FAIR and EOSC from the period 2018-2024, the annual FAIR-IMPACT Synchronisation Force

⁷⁰ Davidson, J., & Pittonet Gaiarin, S. (2025). D2.2 - Final iteration of the FAIR implementation framework (1.0 Not yet approved by the European Commission). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15322176>

⁷¹ FIF Catalogue of Resources; FAIR Implementation Framework Catalogue of Resources , FAIRsharing ID: <https://fairsharing.org/6364>

⁷² <https://fair-impact.eu/synchronisation-force>

⁷³ <https://eosc.eu/sria-mar/>

workshops discussed key topics on the road to more FAIR digital objects, with representatives of more than 120 organisations and projects. Each workshop resulted in a report. Collectively, these formed the basis of a white paper with the main recommendations from these workshops, linking them to the relevant Task Forces and Opportunity Area Expert Groups⁷⁴ under the EOSC Association, to facilitate their uptake and impact.

A dedicated section on the website includes all the information on the Synchronisation Force Workshops.⁷⁵ The first Synchronisation Force workshop series - 2022 edition⁷⁶ took place between November and December 2022, leading to the first report.⁷⁷ The second Synchronisation Force workshop series - 2023 edition⁷⁸ took place a year later, between November 2023 and January 2024, leading to a second report.⁷⁹

The third Synchronisation Force Workshop series - 2024 edition⁸⁰ took place from September to November 2024 and resulted in a third report.⁸¹ The format was the same as previous editions: the project engaged with representatives of key FAIR related projects and initiatives in the EOSC and FAIR ecosystems, from Europe and globally, in a series of online 90 minute interactive sessions. The objective of the workshop series remained the same: discuss common challenges and priorities related to turning the FAIR principles into practice, to then release recommendations to help researchers, data practitioners, scientists as well as decision makers at repository and e-infrastructure level in being more compliant with the FAIR principles for data management. 91 individuals registered for the 2024 workshop series; attendance in individual sessions ranged from 15 to 35 individuals.

The outcomes of the three Synchronisation Force series led to the *“Recommendations for a FAIR EOSC - White Paper of the FAIR-IMPACT Synchronisation Force”*,⁸² providing recommendations for alignment and synchronisation around FAIR practices. All

⁷⁴ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-opportunity-area-expert-groups/>

⁷⁵ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/synchronisation-force-events>

⁷⁶ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/synchronisation-force-events/synchronisation-force-1st-workshop-november-2022>

⁷⁷ Grootveld, M., Pittonet Gaiarin, S., Davidson, J., Dillo, I., O'Connor, R., Marjamaa-Mankinen, L., Verburg, M., & Jonquet, C. (2023). M1.7 - First synchronisation workshop. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7692063>

⁷⁸ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/synchronisation-force-events/synchronisation-force-2nd-workshop-november-2023>

⁷⁹ Grootveld, M., Pittonet Gaiarin, S., Davidson, J., Dillo, I., Verburg, M., Rouchon, O., Priddy, M., Nordling, J., Marjamaa-Mankinen, L., Gonzalez, E., Fink Kjeldgaard, A.-S., David, R., & Dennis, R. (2024). M1.8 - Second synchronisation workshop. Synchronisation Force 2nd Workshop - November 2023. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11082238>

⁸⁰ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/synchronisation-force-workshop-series-2024-edition>

⁸¹ Everhardt, M., Fink, A. S., Jonquet, C., Gonzalez, E., Dillo, I., Nordling, J., Davidson, J., Horton, L., Marjamaa-Mankinen, L., Verburg, M., Priddy, M., GRAU, N., Rouchon, O., & Pittonet Gaiarin, S. (2025). M1.9 Third Synchronisation Workshop Report - 20250211_Graphical version. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14848907>

⁸² Grootveld, M., Fink, A. S., Jonquet, C., González Guardia, E., Dillo, I., Nordling, J., Davidson, J., Marjamaa-Mankinen, L., Verburg, M., Priddy, M., GRAU, N., & Pittonet Gaiarin, S. (2025). D1.3 Recommendations for a FAIR EOSC - White Paper of the FAIR-IMPACT Synchronisation Force (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14979705>

proceedings, reports and the White Paper are uploaded to the FAIR-IMPACT community on Zenodo for long-term preservation and sharing.

7.1. *The Synchronisation Force legacy: 15 recommendations for a FAIR EOSC*

While in-depth recommendations are detailed in the above-mentioned reports, 15 key recommendations have also been collected in a dedicated page on the FAIR-IMPACT website. The 15 recommendations aim to increase FAIRness within the European Open Science Cloud, highlighting six topics, and they are all associated to reports and documents published by the FAIR-IMPACT project that can be used for further reference:

1. Metrics and assessing FAIRness

- Rec. 1: Improve the awareness and uptake of FAIR in the research community by providing a platform of stories and lessons related to the implementation of FAIR and associated benefits.
- Rec. 2: Develop community-lead recommendations and governance for tests, metrics and tools for the assessment of FAIRness, supported by utilising a comprehensive catalogue of methods, metrics and tests.

2. Metadata, semantics and interoperability

- Rec. 3: Enhance metadata and semantics expertise to enable the creation and sharing of FAIR Semantic Artefacts.
- Rec. 4: Develop semantic interoperability through FAIR Semantic Artefacts, via adoption of policies, guidelines and mappings.

3. Persistent identifiers

- Rec. 5: Ensure the interoperability and long-term persistence of PID services and seek convergence of PID systems within a PID stack.
- Rec. 6: Integrate widely used PIDs into researchers' workflows.

4. Legal and organisational interoperability

- Rec. 7: Scale up the knowledge on legal and operational interoperability through a central support programme including training and advice. Support capacity building for Research Infrastructures to acquire and apply such knowledge.
- Rec. 8: Continue collaboration on legal and organisational interoperability in new Horizon Europe projects.
- Rec. 9: Advocate Creative Commons licenses as the default option.

5. Trustworthy and FAIR-enabling repositories

- Rec. 10: Advance transparency in repository processes to increase their trustworthiness.
- Rec. 11: Build an inclusive and collaborative network of TDRs to share experiences and expertise.
- Rec. 12: Provide different kinds of support to help repositories increase their trustworthiness.

6. Sustainability of project outputs

- Rec. 13: Incorporate relevant outputs from EOSC-related projects in the EOSC Federation Handbook.
- Rec. 14: Identify potential sustainability pathways for project outputs.
- Rec. 15: Create a Sustainability Handbook to capture the common challenges, possible solutions and experiences from projects.

7.2. *A Synchronisation Force Blueprint*

Based on the multi-annual experience in the organisation of the Synchronisation Force series, we provide a few recommendations for initiatives that want to embark on similar synchronisation activities in the EOSC landscape.

Start from your courtyard, but aim at going beyond

Invited to the Synchronisation Force workshop were representatives of key FAIR related projects and initiatives in the EOSC framework. Organising collaboration across projects in the same funding call and/or with related remits facilitated the start of the discussion, thanks to the common language and objectives. This was considered useful also because information sharing among existing projects is not always - not exhaustively - facilitated by the funding agencies (EC) and should not be taken for granted. That said, the outcomes turned out to be useful also beyond the European EOSC context. Therefore the recommendation for a similar synchronisation effort is to go beyond the original network already in the workshops series, by inviting to the discussion projects external to the initial network and by providing an element of internationalisation.

Simplify a crowded landscape

Among the main values of the Synchronisation Force workshops, participants referred to the sharing of information in a very crowded landscape, aspects related to convergence and harmonisation, so as to avoid duplication, and the possibility to access knowledge and ideas useful for participants' own work. Asking participants to list in a spreadsheet format, topic by topic, the available resources, with links to authors and reference projects, is a great exercise and a great starting point to then take on in-depth the discussions during the event. It also leaves participants with useful proceedings to refer to. The Synchronisation Force didn't pretend to judge the quality of the information provided by and about so many initiatives: we can't read all deliverables, nor attend all trainings or apply all tools. Asking the project representatives to summarise the most important outcomes and reports facilitated the analysis and was a good way to survey any relevant work.

A clear, doable and recognisable agenda

The format of the Synchronisation Force series was simple, with a similar structure in each of the short-in-time sessions, with clear instructions provided to participants. This facilitated understanding of the needs and made expectations very clear. When planning such topics and community wide activities, splitting the effort into smaller tasks (sessions) requiring limited effort and topic-related attention is useful to keep the interest and the engagement high. The active engagement of participants before and during the event was really high, and several attendees kept up with this during the consecutive sessions of the workshop.

Connect to a broader landscape

The sessions of the Synchronisation Force all started from looking at the current landscape, namely the Strategic Pillars of the EOSC Multi-Annual Roadmap 2026-2027 (MAR 2026-2027) and the relevant Task Forces and Opportunity Area Expert Groups under the EOSC Association, to facilitate their uptake and impact. By mapping FAIR-IMPACT findings and recommendations against the core agenda of the EOSC Partnership and the charters of the main bodies of the EOSC Association, the series engaged in the sessions those involved in the shaping of the EOSC framework, and made them prime movers for the uptake of the resulting recommendations beyond the workshops (and beyond the FAIR-IMPACT project results).

Sustain the Synchronisation Force

The Synchronisation Force function is highly relevant for a large number of stakeholders in the ecosystem. The value of the Synchronisation Force relies not just on the assessment of the implementation of the FAIR principles across initiatives and projects, but also, and most of all, on the dialogue and the discussion mechanisms the Synchronisation Force facilitates. The financial support for the organisation of the workshop covers the manpower of the organising committee, the licensing costs for the online meeting tool and costs associated with marketing and promotional activities, while participants all come on a voluntary or in-kind effort. While it is relatively small, the financial support is nonetheless fundamental, and must be foreseen before the projects start and preferably when there is still room to allocate capacity to the collaboration. Sharing of the managing costs among different projects involved in the initial phase could be a good practice.

Taking over the Synchronisation Force efforts

Among the entities that were suggested as potential take-overs of the Synchronisation Force series, the EOSC Association and its Opportunity Areas, and the Research Data Alliance were mentioned.

8. FAIR Champions as ambassadors for the project

The group of 13 EOSC FAIR Champions⁸³ selected to act as ambassadors for FAIR, were actively engaged in different activities also in this reporting period. Their engagement in this last reporting period is reported below:

Sarah Barber, Affiliation: Eastern Switzerland University of Applied Sciences, Country: Switzerland. Discuss about the collaboration with the wind energy community with respect to semantic artefact. Sara Hosted WP4 members (Clément Jonquet) giving a talk into Sarah Barber's group.

Camilla Hagen Blixhavn, Affiliation: University of Oslo, Country: Norway. Facilitator of the FAIR National Roadshow in Norway, organised on 16th September 2024.

Giulia Caldoni, Affiliation: University of Bologna, Country: Italy. Actively disseminated FAIR-IMPACT outcomes to the National chapter for Data Steward Community (Italy, Bologna), in collaboration with GARR through Skills4EOSC; participation in the Synchronisation Force 2024; facilitator, co-organiser and speaker at the Italian National Roadshow in Genova, 8 April 2025; speaker at the “FAIR Implementation Workshop - What is a ‘Data Champion’ and how can they support good practice in data management and sharing?” on 16th April, part of the FAIR Implementation workshop series.

Javier de la Cueva, Affiliation: University of the Instituto de Empresa, Country: Spain. Participation in the Synchronisation Force 2024; recording of a podcast on Legal interoperability in collaboration with the FAIR Data podcast⁸⁴, July 2024; participation to the FAIRfest as a speaker during the session “I for Interoperability”, 20 February 2025.

Romain David, Affiliation: ERINHA AISBL, Country: Belgium. Participation in the Synchronisation Force 2024 and co-author of the Second synchronisation workshop post event report; participation as speaker in the “FAIR Implementation Workshop - Where do I start with FAIRification of sensitive data?” that took place on 25th June. Romain is also co-author of two articles published by the Data Science Journal around the importance of DMP in sharing research best practices. The articles are part of the collection “Data Management Planning across Disciplines and Infrastructures”⁸⁵ dedicated to provide an overview of challenges, opportunities and concepts in using DMPs across disciplines and infrastructures. Romain was also a mentor in the FAIRness assessment challenge support action where he brought some perspective and connections with the OSCARS project⁸⁶.

Richard Dennis, Affiliation: Novo Nordisk Foundation Center for Stem Cell Medicine, University of Copenhagen, Country: Denmark. Facilitator, co-organiser and speaker at the

⁸³ <https://fair-impact.eu/eosc-fair-champions>

⁸⁴ <https://fair-impact.eu/news/fair-data-podcast1-unlocking-fair-interoperability-navigating-legal-aspects>

⁸⁵ <https://datascience.codata.org/collections/data-management-planning>

⁸⁶ <https://oscars-project.eu/>

Danish National Roadshow, 8 October 2024⁸⁷; Participation in the Synchronisation Force 2024 and co-author of the Second synchronisation workshop post event report;

Anandhi Iyappan, Affiliation: EMBL, Country: Germany. Actively disseminated FAIR-IMPACT outcomes to the EMBL community.

Mari Kleemola, Affiliation: Finnish Social Science Data Archive, Country: Finland. Facilitator, co-organiser and speaker at the Finish National Roadshow, May 2024⁸⁸; Participation in the Synchronisation Force 2024.

Fotis Mystakopoulos, Affiliation: OPERAS AISBL, Country: Greece. Facilitator for the National Roadshow in Greece, 18 November 2024⁸⁹; keynote speaker at the FAIR Implementation workshop dedicated to “Examples of national initiatives for FAIR: Greece and the Netherlands”, part of the second running of the FAIR-IMPACT support programme for National Level Initiatives, delivered on 29 November 2024⁹⁰.

Antonio Novellino, Affiliation: ETT SpA, Country: Italy. Link with the Ocean data community and the Blue-Cloud 2026 initiative, participation in the Synchronisation Force 2024; facilitator, co-organiser and speaker at the Italian National Roadshow in Genova, 8 April 2025.

Susanna-Assunta Sansone, Affiliation: Oxford e-Research Centre, Country: United Kingdom. Mentor for the Support offer #4: “Improving the availability and machine readability of data policies with FAIRsharing.

9. Events

FAIR-IMPACT organised several types of events, aiming to reach different audiences for different purposes, while promoting project results next to different communities. In the following sections it is available a detailed description of each typology of events organised. Important to mention that each one of these events counted with wide dissemination campaigns throughout different channels to increase the number of participants.

⁸⁷

<https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/fair-principles-national-and-institutional-data-management-policies>

⁸⁸ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/national-roadshows/fair-impact-national-roadshow-finland>

⁸⁹

<https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/implementing-fair-principles-tools-infrastructure-and-guidelines-and>

⁹⁰ <https://zenodo.org/records/15045110>

9.1. FAIR-IMPACT Workshops on third party events

The project had active roles in different third-party events in Europe and beyond, where FAIR-IMPACT workshops were organised. These events were either organised by FAIR-IMPACT, while others were organised with other projects from the EOSC umbrella, with which FAIR-IMPACT joined forces in supporting the adoption of FAIR practices across Europe. Below we report about the many different workshops and sessions organised by FAIR-IMPACT in conjunction with third party events and initiatives.

9.1.1. RDA Plenaries co-located workshops

At the **RDA 2024 and 2025 plenaries** (Sweden⁹¹ and Costa Rica⁹² respectively) workshops were organised. **In 2024, organised along with FAIRCORE4EOSC, the workshop “Research Software Workshop: guidelines and metrics for metadata curation”**, with the goal of collecting existing guidelines for research software and identify the gaps with the Scholarly infrastructures for Research Software (SIRS) Report, from the EOSC Executive Board Working Group Architecture Task Force. The workshop also aimed to review CodeMeta initiative vocabulary and its crosswalk table to extend interoperability, as well as discuss curation mechanisms for Research Software to improve the metadata quality. **In 2025, at Costa Rica, the workshop “Interoperability Frameworks in a Global Perspective”** was designed for individuals actively engaged in developing or implementing interoperability frameworks or research commons.

Figure 11: FAIR-IMPACT Official custom-made images to promote the workshops at RDA Plenaries

9.1.2. Visibility at the EOSC events

Within the EOSC landscape events, FAIR-IMPACT organised 3 workshops at the **EOSC Symposium 2022**:⁹³

⁹¹<https://fair-impact.eu/events/fairimpact-events/research-software-workshop-guidelines-and-metrics-metadata-curation>

⁹²<https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/interoperability-frameworks-global-perspective-fair-impact-co-located>

⁹³ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/other-fair-events/eosc-symposium-2022>

- **"EOSC PID Policy and FAIRCORE4EOSC Measuring Compliance": organised with FAIRCORE4EOSC:** engage end users and the EOSC community to confirm the scope of the policy and mechanisms to measure and confirm compliance;
- **"Semantic Interoperability in EOSC": organised with FAIRCORE4EOSC:** propose an interoperability strategy that allows for format, schema and data type diversity, and facilitates interoperability where needed but remains manageable
- **"Towards a shared value proposition for Persistent Identifiers in EOSC":** facilitate a community discussion on this topic.

To add to FAIR-IMPACT contribution to the EOSC Symposium 2022, a **joint-talk with Skills4EOSC** entitled "Engaging stakeholder communities in Skills4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT" to demonstrate how both projects were going to work to foster two-way engagement with different stakeholder communities to build capacity and to support the adoption of Open Science and FAIR-enabling practices. Furthermore, FAIR-IMPACT project coordinator joined a panel discussion focused on Interoperability.

At the **EOSC Winter School 2025**,⁹⁴ the final FAIR-IMPACT interoperability workshop "Future Perfect: EOSC Building Blocks from the FAIR-IMPACT Past and Present" was organised. It was an event to maximise the utility of the previous workshop results in the EOSC context organised at RDA Plenary Costa Rica.

Figure 12: FAIR-IMPACT Official Promotional Image for the workshop at EOSC Winter School 2025

9.1.3. Contribution to other third party events

⁹⁴<https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/fair-impact-announces-co-located-final-interoperability-workshop-eosc>

During the project timeframe, FAIR-IMPACT was promoted at **over 90 third-party events** (see Annex 2). The visibility was reached through presentations, organisation of joint workshops, presence at panel discussions, exhibition booths and poster/paper submissions. Below we mention a few where FAIR-IMPACT actively contributed to the programme.

FAIR-IMPACT joined the **EUDAT Conference 2024⁹⁵** to organise a workshop entirely focused on **"Semantics for FAIR & FAIR Semantics"**, to highlight community-driven initiatives around semantic artefacts and introduce recommendations, guidelines, and services developed within EOSC-related projects.

Figure 13: FAIR-IMPACT Promotional Image for the workshops at EUDAT Conference 2024

Continuing the series of FAIR-IMPACT workshops organised by FAIR-IMPACT at IDCC24 (workshops 2, 3 and 6: <https://dcc.ac.uk/events/idcc25/workshop-programme>), In February 2025, at the **International Digital Curation Center Conference 2025⁹⁶**, FAIR-IMPACT organised two workshops:

- **"Supporting Communities in implementing FAIR Principles for Open Science"**, focused on general guidance for various stakeholder groups to engage in the adoption of relevant workflows to enable FAIR research, the reliable tracing of research outputs and impact. FAIR metrics, Persistent Identifiers, Metadata and Semantic, Data Interoperability.
- **"Building a CoreTrustSeal community with DANS and FAIR-IMPACT"**, to discuss the topic of community building around CoreTrustSeal.

⁹⁵ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/fair-impact-semantic-session-eudat-conference-2024>

⁹⁶ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/fair-impact-19th-international-digital-curation-conference-idcc25> & <https://dcc.ac.uk/events/idcc25/workshop-programme>

2025 International Digital Curation Conference

Workshop 4
13:00 - 16:30 CET | 17 February 2025

Supporting communities in implementing FAIR principles for Open Science

Delivered by:

eosc | FAIR-IMPACT

Figure 14: FAIR-IMPACT Promotional Image for the workshops at IDCC 2025.

9.2. FAIR-IMPACT events

Besides organising workshops at third-party events, FAIR-IMPACT also organised its stand-alone events, focusing on different aspects of FAIR data practices.

Starting from a generic overview, in January 2024 (half-way of FAIR-IMPACT project), the **“FAIR-IMPACT Community Event”**⁹⁷ took place, to discuss the work FAIR-IMPACT has been undertaking, collect feedback from the people and teams who are currently receiving FAIR dedicated support through our open calls, as well as debate with 179 people who registered on specific topics related to the driving themes of the project. It was a crucial event to identify potential new topics and lines of action for the second half period of the project.

⁹⁷ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/fair-impact-community-event>

Figure 15: FAIR-IMPACT Official Promotional Image Community Event

9.3. FAIR-IMPACT topics related workshops

FAIR-IMPACT also organised a **series of workshops to discuss issues around mappings and crosswalks** and how they can become shareable and reusable, i.e. FAIR, elevating them to “first class” citizens in the FAIR data world. All together, these workshops recruited a total number of almost 400 individuals.

Several workshops were organised and the first one took place in April 2023, entitled “**Why Mappings Matter and how to make them FAIR?**”,⁹⁸ which was focused on demonstrating to the audience how they could benefit from mappings. This workshop was followed by another one in November of 2023, entitled “**Developing a mapping process framework**”,⁹⁹ it counted with several short presentations of community mapping strategies and was followed by a discussion on common steps and most useful existing strategies. In April 2024, a third workshop was organised, entitled “**Developing a mapping process framework**”¹⁰⁰ to analyse common components of a mapping process to formalise a mapping process framework, based on the outputs of previous workshops and FAIR-IMPACT analysis.

⁹⁸ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fairimpact-events/why-mappings-matter-and-how-make-them-fair>

⁹⁹ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/documenting-mapping-community-practices>

¹⁰⁰ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/developing-mapping-process-framework>

Figure 16 FAIR-IMPACT Official Promotional Images several mappings workshops

Another workshop, with a topic related to the previous 3 workshops referred, was organised in September 2023, an hybrid format workshop was organised (online & in Lecce, Italy) and was entitled **“Semantic Artefact Governance Workshop”**.¹⁰¹ It was co-located with the OntoPortal Workshop 2023 and was dedicated to define best practices for managing semantic artefact and ontologies.

Focusing on PIDs, a total of two workshops were organised, both in 2023. The first one was in May entitled **“PID best practices for complex data citation, semantic artefacts and related services”**¹⁰² and the second in November entitled **“EOSC Compliant PID Implementations - Practical Guidelines for Implementing Best Practices”**.¹⁰³ The first one counted with the participation of relevant projects and initiatives to provide an update on their related work and the ambition is to work together on defining community best practices on PIDs and complex data citation. The second workshop demonstrated concrete tools, policies and developments within the realm of PIDs from the EOSC projects. Important to mention that several of these tools were considered during the provision of some of the FAIR-IMPACT Open Support Calls that were organised in 2024.

Figure 17: FAIR-IMPACT Official Promotional Images for the PIDs workshops

¹⁰¹ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/fair-impact-semantic-artefact-governance-workshop>

¹⁰² <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/pid-best-practices-complex-data-citation-semantic-artefacts-and-related-services>

¹⁰³ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/eosc-compliant-pid-implementations-practical-guidelines-for-implementing-best-practices>

A workshop focused on metadata was organised in May 2023, entitled **“Developing Guidelines for Metadata Collection and Curation for Research Software”**,¹⁰⁴ to present FAIR-IMPACT guidelines for the collection and curation of metadata to archive, reference, describe and cite research software.

Figure 18: FAIR-IMPACT Official Promotional Image for the Metadata workshop

These stand-alone workshops from FAIR-IMPACT, which focused on different aspects of FAIR data practices, were further explored either in the workshops organised at third-party events, as well as on the FAIR-IMPACT National Roadshows, FAIR Implementation Workshops and through "traditional" presentations and poster presentations at third-party events, described in the following chapters.

9.4. National Roadshows

The series of National Roadshows¹⁰⁵ was conceived as online or on-site events with the aim of speeding up FAIR adoption by communities in different European countries, thanks to the engagement with local facilitators who are chosen strategically to identify the topic of the event, the target community and the channels for promotion. 14 roadshows were organised during the FAIR-IMPACT project, 10 of which between June 2024 and May 2025. They extended the network of projects and initiatives that FAIR-IMPACT already collaborated with, introducing channels to promote FAIR-IMPACT recommendations, good practices, and tools. These roadshows were a key instrument to engage the national level

¹⁰⁴<https://fair-impact.eu/events/fairimpact-events/developing-guidelines-metadata-collection-and-curation-research-software>

¹⁰⁵ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/national-roadshows>

stakeholders, which were an explicit focus of the FAIR-IMPACT project for community engagement.

Roadshow	Type	Date	Number of registered participants
France	Hybrid	11 September 2024	191
Romania	Online	8 October 2024	183
The Netherlands	Hybrid	17 October 2024	131
Germany	Online	24 January 2024	104
Italy	Hybrid	8 April 2025	103
Serbia	Online	10 October 2023	80
Slovenia	Online	28 September 2023	72
Austria	Online	18 June 2024	62
Greece	Online	18 November 2024	55
Norway	Hybrid	16 September 2024	51
Denmark	Online	4 October 2024	49
Finland	Online	17 May 2024	46
UK	Physical	12 May 2025	36
Tunisia	Online	25 September 2024	25

Table 1: number of participants registered to each of the National Roadshows

Figure 19: Geographical distribution of registered participants to the National roadshows in Europe (Tunisia is missing)

Among the outcome resulting from the organisation of such roadshows we can mention the following:

- positive effect on connecting together different representatives of various stakeholders from the same country, facilitating networking and sharing of knowledge and information about projects and initiatives which are not always properly connected (i.e. Italy, Greece)
- for the roadshows organised during the first part of the project, the events gave visibility to the open calls and stimulated participation to the expert and financial support actions (Serbia, Slovenia)
- Some direct connections were created between the roadshows and the national level initiatives, in some cases with a roadshow that stimulated application to the the 2nd support programme (Croatia, Romania, Tunisia), and in other cases the other way round, with a roadshow resulting from the connections established within the NLI programme (Italy, UK)

The National Roadshow model

To structure and facilitate the organisation of the events, a similar approach was adopted and replicated across the series, which includes the following:

- **Facilitator at country level.** As a first step, one or more national facilitators were identified at the start, chosen strategically to identify the topic of the event, the target community and the channels for promotion. National facilitators included universities and national Open Science coordinators and were coupled with a representative of FAIR-IMPACT outreach & dissemination team.
- **Link with the EOSC Mandated organisations.** All the roadshows were organised in collaboration with EOSC Mandated Organisations in the country who were invited to moderate the event, and promoted through the EOSC Association channels.
- **Semi-structured agenda.** A combination of fixed and optional modules was provided to the facilitators and event organisers to start drafting the event agenda.
- **National topic & target stakeholders.** The topic of each roadshow was adapted to the needs and level of awareness of the national target audience.
- **Reuse of materials.** FAIRsFAIR presentations were at the disposal of colleagues across the roadshows. This ensured effort and knowledge optimisation, and efficiency in the event organisation. In addition, collaboration and sharing of the materials were central to the organisation of the roadshows.
- **Flexibility.** Language, agenda, registration process, and location were adjusted to accommodate facilitator and participant needs.

9.5. FAIR-IMPACT Webinars

Focusing on the **FAIR-IMPACT support programmes**, 13 webinars were organised to provide information to potential applications of each one of the six launched open calls, followed by an additional webinar before the launch of the call to provide support on last minute questions applicants may have in their applications. In total, over 660 individuals

attended these webinars, supporting FAIR-IMPACT to reach a higher number of applications. Details about registered participants are provided in Annex 2.

Figure 20: FAIR-IMPACT Official custom-made images to promote the Open Calls Webinars

9.6. FAIRfest

The final event of **FAIR-IMPACT**, organised jointly with **FAIRCORE4EOSC**, was the “FAIRfest - Celebrating advancements of FAIR solutions in EOSC”,¹⁰⁶ that took place in The Hague (The Netherlands), right after the IDCC 2025 conference, to capitalise on the presence of a wide community of individuals being already in the area, interested in open science and FAIR practices.

The FAIRfest, which lasted 1 day and half, was a festival celebrating advancements of FAIR solutions in the European Open Science research landscape. It brought together European and international participants to explore the latest achievements in FAIR: Persistent Identifiers and Knowledge Graphs for Findability, Semantic Artefacts for Accessibility, technical and legal aspects for Interoperability, and certification, metrics, and guidelines for Reusability.

The festival featured a vibrant **Marketplace where 15 adopters and implementers**, through 10 minute pitches, showcased FAIR-enabling solutions, tools, methodologies, and practices through stands, coffee tables, and posters. Attendees engaged directly with experts, asked questions, and learned from those already applying FAIR in real research contexts. **Demonstrations of FAIRCORE4EOSC components were presented**, and participants heard implementation stories from teams supported by the FAIR-IMPACT programme. The event also offered **opportunities to meet FAIR Champions, ambassadors, and interoperability specialists**, creating a dynamic environment for exchange and collaboration.

FAIRfest counted more than 333 attendees, 233 in The Hague and 100 who joined online. The majority of the audience was from Europe, but it also counted with participants outside Europe (e.g. Japan, Canada, Australia and USA).

¹⁰⁶ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/fairfest-celebrating-advancements-fair-solutions-eosc>

Figure 21: Group picture of one of the panels at the FAIRfest

Figure 22: FAIRfest marketplace area

A post-event report¹⁰⁷ was published on 17th April, with a more detailed overview of the topics discussed at the event and, by the time of writing this report, it counted with 202 views. A photo gallery¹⁰⁸ was also made available and a recap overall video¹⁰⁹ was published as well on FAIR-IMPACT YouTube Channel.

10. Publications and Scientific papers

FAIR-IMPACT released 176 pieces of documentation that have been published as open access resources on the project community on Zenodo. They include deliverables, reports, white papers, presentations, posters and training materials. They have been sign-posted on the FAIR-IMPACT website in the sections “deliverables and milestones”¹¹⁰ and “publications and others”¹¹¹ and linked to specific pages (such as the Implementation stories¹¹²), to facilitate retrieval from the website.

FAIR-IMPACT partners also published 9 peer reviewed papers on journals and conference proceedings. The papers are focused on several FAIR principles aspects, namely digital objects, semantics and ontologies.

Type	Publication
1 Article in Journal	Soiland-Reyes S, Castro LJ, Garijo D, Portier M, Goble C, Groth P (2022) Updating Linked Data practices for FAIR Digital Object principles. Research Ideas and Outcomes 8: e94501. https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.8.e94501
2 Article in Journal	Rudolf Wittner, Petr Holub, Cecilia Mascia, Francesca Frexia, Heimo Müller, Markus Plass, Clare Allocca, Fay Betsou, Tony Burdett, Ibon Cancio, Adriane Chapman, Martin Chapman, Mélanie Courtot, Vasa Curcin, Johann Eder, Mark Elliot, Katrina Exter, Carole Goble, Martin Golebiewski, Bron Kisler, Andreas Kremer, Simone Leo, Sheng Lin-Gibson, Anna Marsano, Marco Mattavelli, Josh Moore, Hiroki Nakae, Isabelle Perseil, Ayat Salman, James Sluka, Stian Soiland-Reyes, Caterina Strambio-De-Castillia, Michael Sussman, Jason R. Swedlow, Kurt

¹⁰⁷ Adloff, F., Davidson, J., Fink, A. S., Gruenpeter, M., Jonquet, C., Kalaitzi, V., Pittonet Gaiarin, S., Nordling, J., Suominen, T., van de Sanden, M., Verburg, M., & D'Onofrio, C. (2025). FAIRfest: Celebrating advancements of FAIR solutions in EOSC_post event report. FAIRfest: Celebrating advancements of FAIR solutions in EOSC, The Hague, The Netherlands. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15234134>

¹⁰⁸ <https://www.flickr.com/photos/202331412@N03/sets/72177720324101355/>

¹⁰⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RcO6Z-rgPXA>

¹¹⁰ <https://fair-impact.eu/deliverables-milestones>

¹¹¹ <https://fair-impact.eu/publications>

¹¹² <https://fair-impact.eu/implementation-adoption-stories>

Type		Publication
		Zatloukal, Jörg Geiger (2023) Toward a common standard for data and specimen provenance in life sciences https://doi.org/10.1002/lrh2.10365
3	Article in Journal	Zwölf, C.M., Moreau, N. Assessment of the FAIRness of the Virtual Atomic and Molecular Data Centre following the Research Data Alliance evaluation framework. <i>Eur. Phys. J. D</i> 77 , 70 (2023). https://doi.org/10.1140/epjd/s10053-023-00649-x
4	Other	Saldanha Bach, J., Klas, C.-P., Mathiak, B., Yudong Zhang, & Mutschke, P. (2023). FAIRness assessment: a comparison of the RDA model and the F-UJI Automated tool report (1.0, p. 58 p.). GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8308902
5	Publication in Conference Proceedings/ Workshop	Jonquet, C.; Poveda-Villalon, M. (2023) About versioning ontologies or any digital objects with clear semantics https://doi.org/10.4126/FRL01-006444994
6	Publication in Conference Proceedings/ Workshop	Gonzalez, E.; Garijo, D.; Corcho, O.; Palma, R.; Wolniewicz, M.; Rynkiewicz, A. (2023) FAIR Research Object Assessment: A landscape analysis https://doi.org/10.4126/FRL01-006444989
7	Article in Journal	Tarallo, A., Pulieri, M., Ramezani, P., & Rosati, I. (2024). Advancements in EcoPortal: Enhancing functionalities for the ecological domain semantic artefacts repository. <i>FAIR Connect</i> , 2(1), 1-7 https://doi.org/10.3233/FC-240002
8	Publication in Conference Proceedings/ Workshop	Jonquet, C. <i>et al.</i> (2023). Ontology Repositories and Semantic Artefact Catalogues with the OntoPortal Technology. In: Payne, T.R., <i>et al.</i> The Semantic Web – ISWC 2023. ISWC 2023. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 14266. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-47243-5_3
9	Publication in Conference Proceedings/ Workshop	María Poveda-Villalon, Daniel Garijo, Alejandra Gonzalez-Beltran, Clement Jonquet, Yann Le Franc. Ontology Engineering and the FAIR principles: A Gap Analysis toward a FAIR-by-design methodology. <i>FOAM 2024 - FAIR principles for Ontologies and Metadata in Knowledge Management</i> , C. Trojahn; D. Garijo; M. Poveda Villalón; C. Henrique Bernabé; A. Yu Lin, Jul 2024, Enschede, Netherlands. 15p. https://hal.science/hal-04678381/

Table 2: FAIR-IMPACT peer-reviewed articles and papers

11. Online Communications and outcomes

11.1. Social Media

Throughout the FAIR-IMPACT project, social media channels have played a crucial role in promoting activities, building community engagement, and ensuring wide visibility. The platforms most actively used were LinkedIn and X (formerly Twitter), followed by YouTube and Zenodo. The social media channels acted as valuable amplification tools. Through a planned and consistent content calendar, the outreach team guaranteed ongoing visibility for the project's initiatives, such as events, webinars, news updates, and key announcements. This strategic use of social media also strengthened community building, creating a pathway for individuals to move from casual viewers of our posts to becoming actively engaged stakeholders.

11.1.1. LinkedIn

On LinkedIn, the project maintained a consistent posting frequency of at least one to two posts per week, with higher peaks during major events. Each post was carefully structured to include a clear title, a description of the content, and a call to action (CTA) to encourage further engagement. The content varied across key themes such as event announcements, news or published articles, brand awareness initiatives, surveys, and the promotion of multimedia materials.

Total LinkedIn Followers (as of May 2025): 1,232

Follower demographics

Figure 23: Follower demographics of FAIR-IMPACT LinkedIn channel

Example of LinkedIn posts:

FAIR-IMPACT EU Project
1,203 followers
2mo • Edited •

The A for Accessibility session continues at #FAIRfest!

- **Morane Gruenpeter** presented **Research Software MetaData (RSMD)** guidelines and the CodeMeta standard & initiative, highlighting how they contribute to the #EOSC vision for software metadata.
- **Yann Le Franc** from **e-Science Data Factory** & Joonas Kesäniemi (CSC) delivered a presentation on **FAIR mappings recommendations and the MSCR service**. They showed how RDA FAIR Mapping WG represents a path to sustainability and how #Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR)
- **Clement Jonquet** from **INRAE** illustrated **FAIR Semantic Artefact and their Catalogues**. He showed that Semantic Artefact Catalogues (SAC) are a key component of the EOSC #Interoperability Framework.

"In FAIR-IMPACT, we strongly relied on **OntoPortal** and made this **SAC technology stronger to support FAIR SAS**" – Clement Jonquet

- **Hans Lienhop** from **GWDG - Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung mbH Göttingen** explained **DTR on the roadmap of implementing FDOs**. In particular, he focused on The Data Type Registry and The Data Type Registry.

🗣️ The session is now involved in a **panel discussion** where the speakers are engaging with the audience in a Q&A and debate.

FAIR-IMPACT EU Project
1,203 followers
1mo • Edited •

FAIR National Roadshow comes to Italy! IT

Join us for the next stop in the FAIR National Roadshow series: "FAIR ...more

👍 21 7 reposts

Like Comment Repost

FAIR-IMPACT EU Project
1,203 followers
1mo • Edited •

FAIR Enough? The Case for Discipline-Specific Metrics

As part of the **FAIR-IMPACT EU Project**, we've been exploring discipline-specific metrics for the Social Sciences to enable more precise #FAIR evaluations using the F-ujii tool. While the #FAIRprinciples (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) provide a broad framework, tailored metrics help ensure #datasets meet discipline-specific standards.

- 📊 Our recent survey gathered insights from 29 professionals across IT, data management, and research, uncovering key challenges and opportunities:
- ✅ **High engagement with FAIR principles**—73.1% apply them in their work.
- ✅ **Limited awareness of discipline-specific FAIR metrics**—only 36.4% had encountered them.
- ✅ **A clear preference for bottom-up development**—led by researchers and support staff rather than mandates.
- ✅ **Resource constraints**—lack of time (61.9%), funding (38.1%), and skills (33.3%) hinder adoption.

📌 The findings reveal a strong interest in discipline-specific #FAIRmetrics but also highlight the need for more support and collaboration. **So, how FAIR is your field?**

🔗 **Read the full insights here and join the conversation:**
<https://lnkd.in/dbFbepgy>

Survey results on discipline specific metrics
fair-impact.eu

FAIR-IMPACT EU Project
1,203 followers
1mo •

Going LIVE: Assess Your Data's FAIRness with F-UJI!

Are your datasets truly #FAIR? Find out NOW in our live workshop at 13:00 CET! 🕒

Join us for a **hands-on session on F-UJI**, the powerful tool that automatically assesses the #FAIRness of your #data. **Robert Huber (University of Bremen)** is now providing a session on discipline specific capabilities.

- What's in store next?
- ✅ Insights from #FAIRassessments in social sciences
- ✅ Step-by-step demo to assess your own datasets
- ✅ Live Q&A with experts

🕒 **LIVE NOW | 20th March 2025 | 13:00 - 14:00 CET**
🔗 **Register now (it's free!):** <https://lnkd.in/d/f5-A9hA>

Session overview

- Welcome
- F-UJI Introduction and Discipline Specific Capabilities
- Experience with Discipline Specific Metrics (Social Sciences)
- How to use F-UJI on your datasets
 - Local instance
 - Web application
- Q&A
- Wrap up

Figure 24: examples of LinkedIn posts

11.1.2. X (Former Twitter)

The same strategic approach was applied to X, with regular posting of one post weekly and intensified activity around key events. Posts were structured similarly, ensuring consistency

across platforms and supporting a coherent communication strategy. The thematic focus mirrored that of LinkedIn, targeting a wide professional audience with tailored messages based on the type of content shared.

Total X Followers (as of May 2025): 1,243

Figure 25. Examples of X posts

11.1.3. Youtube

Throughout the project, video content has played an important role in supporting communication and dissemination activities. WP2 contributed to the creation, design, and promotion of various types of video materials, including interviews, tutorials, and recordings from events. YouTube was employed as a platform to host a range of multimedia outputs. Several videos from project events were uploaded on the FAIR-IMPACT Channel¹¹³, alongside interviews and podcasts, enhancing both the visibility and accessibility of FAIR-IMPACT activities.

Since the launch of the project, the channel has steadily grown its audience and, as of April 2025, has recorded a total of 1.5 million impressions and 4.0k views from impressions.

Several Playlists have been created to facilitate and organise content on the platform. The playlists are:

- National Roadshow
- FAIR Implementation and Open Calls for Support
- Synchronisation Force
- World Digital Preservation Day 2022
- Interviews

Below is a table presenting the most recent updates of the videos uploaded to YouTube. Since the last published milestone (March 2024), a total of 28 videos have been published.

#	Video Link and Title
1	FAIR-IMPACT's virtual clinic for potential applicants to the second open call for fina...
2	FAIR-IMPACT Implementation Workshop: French Data Management Clusters
3	FAIR-IMPACT Workshop - Developing a mapping process framework
4	FAIR-IMPACT's 2nd open call for repository support programme
5	FAIR-IMPACT Finland National Roadshow - Benefits of EOSC and international colla...
6	FAIR Implementation Workshop - Assessing national current FAIR-enabling capabil...
7	FAIR-IMPACT's Virtual Clinic for potential applicants to 2nd OpenCall for repository...
8	FAIR-IMPACT National Roadshow Austria - Advancing Research Data Management ...
9	Where do I start with FAIRification of sensitive data?

¹¹³ <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCz8RtVeclVYTFMJT6d9Ne0w>

#	Video Link and Title
10	Skills4EOSC Minimum Viable Skills Profiles Implementation using FAIR Signposting
11	FAIR-IMPACT National Roadshow France - French data repositories and their use o...
12	FAIR National Roadshow Norway - Data Interoperability: From Discussion to Practi...
13	FAIR National Roadshow Tunisia - Advancing FAIR Policies and Practices in Tunisia
14	FAIR National Roadshow Denmark - FAIR national & institutional data manageme...
15	FAIR-IMPACT National Roadshow Romania: Collaborative FAIR Data Practices & Tools
16	Webinar to introduce FAIR-IMPACT's final open call for financial support
17	FAIR-IMPACT's virtual clinic for potential applicants to the third open call for finan...
18	Implementing FAIR principles: Tools, Infrastructure and Guidelines and the Greek ...
19	FAIR principles and practices for the Dutch Research Data Management Community
20	FAIR Implementation Workshop on Repository Trust Resources: Pick & Mix for you...
21	FAIR Implementation Workshop on Exploring Costs and Incentives for Data Manag...
22	FAIRfest: Celebrating advancements of FAIR solutions in EOSC
23	FAIR Implementation Workshop - Using F UJI to Assess the FAIRness of your Data
24	FAIR Implementation Workshop - OAIS version 3 What does it mean for repositories
25	FAIR Implementation Workshop - The Hungarian Research Network's Research Dat...
26	FAIR assessments for Research Quality Evaluation and reproducibility_FAIR Nation...
27	AnaEE research infrastructure SemData October2024
28	FAIR Implementation Workshop-Meet the SoftWare Hash Identifier: Do one thing ...

Table 3 : List of Youtube videos uploaded from March 2024 until April 2025

11.2. FAIR-IMPACT Zenodo community

All materials produced during FAIR-IMPACT-organised events—including flyers, presentation slides, and other related resources—were systematically uploaded to the project's Zenodo account. This ensured that all outputs remained publicly accessible and

citable. Since the launch of Zenodo, the FAIR-IMPACT platform counts 181 submissions, further contributing to the dissemination and long-term preservation of FAIR-IMPACT's work. Furthermore, two communities have been created: the FAIR-IMPACT Community and the FAIRfest 2025 Community. Below, are the banners of the two communities:

Figure 26: FAIR-IMPACT and FAIRfest 2025 Communities on Zenodo

11.3. Website

The FAIR-IMPACT website has acted as the primary digital platform for the project's communication and stakeholder engagement. Over time, additional sections have been integrated, building on the initial structure outlined in D7.1, to enhance the website's scope and functionality. The website prominently displayed ongoing activities on the homepage, accompanied by a clear call to action, encouraging visitors to engage (see image below).

Figure 27: FAIR-IMPACT Homepage hero highlighting the FAIR Implementation workshop series.

A revamp of the website homepage and of the information architecture is currently undergoing to ensure the key results from the projects will be showcased after its end. The current information architecture is the one presented below:

Figure 28: FAIR-IMPACT website current information architecture

Active users ▾ by Country

COUNTRY	ACTIVE USERS
United Kingdom	1.4K
Netherlands	1.2K
France	868
Italy	828
Romania	563
Germany	548
United States	448

Figure 29: website active users by country. Source: Google Analytics , April 2024-April 2025

Note to the website traffic figures

Concerning traffic to the project website, since the beginning we adopted a strict approach to user consent and cookies on the web platform. As a consequence of that, no cookie for the purpose of traffic and website usage statistics (Google Analytics) is allowed without explicit visitor consent. From the beginning of the project to May 2025, the analytics cookie acceptance rate has been 31,21%, and therefore views and sessions are monitored on this overall percentage of traffic.

11.4. Newsletters

The newsletter has been another essential channel for keeping stakeholders informed about the project's developments. FAIR-IMPACT consistently distributed newsletters to its contact database via email, maintaining regular communication throughout the project's duration. The email marketing platform adopted by the FAIR-IMPACT project is "Mailjet".

In line with FAIR-IMPACT's communication strategy, emails were sent only when there were meaningful updates to share. This approach was adopted to avoid sending messages merely to fulfil a schedule, thereby ensuring that stakeholders received only valuable and timely information without being overwhelmed by excessive direct communication. Email addresses were collected through registration forms linked to events, webinars, and workshops organised by the project.

As of the final reporting period, the FAIR-IMPACT newsletter has reached a subscriber base of 1,441 contacts and a total of 21 Newsletters have been sent out. Over the past year (March 2024-April 2025), a total of 13,252 emails have been sent, achieving an open rate of 48.13% and a click-through rate of 55.03%.

The chart below shows statistics of the newsletter engagement between March 2024 and April 2025

Chart

Months ▾

Figure 30: Statistics of the newsletter engagement between March 2024 and April 2025

The image below provides an example of a typical newsletter. It illustrates how each communication reflected the project's brand identity, featured a clear structure, and always concluded with a strong call to action to encourage further engagement.

Figure 30: Example of FAIR-IMPACT Newsletter

Below, a table summarises all newsletters sent to date, highlighting the main topics covered and their respective distribution dates. Direct links to read them online are provided on the FAIR-IMPACT communication kit.¹¹⁴

# Issue	Title issue	Distribution Date
21	FAIRfest Event-Report is Out! Upcoming FAIR Implementation Workshops, Synchronisation Force final reports, New Blog on "OAIS version 3 & more	22 April 2025
20	Upcoming events, our podcast, updates from the newly launched FIDELIS initiative: FAIR-IMPACT Spring Season Newsletter is out!	2 April 2025
19	FAIR Implementation Workshop Series	13 March 2025
18	Follow the FAIRfest! Special issue of the FAIR-IMPACT newsletter	17 February 2025
17	🌟 Wishing You a FAIRfestive Season! 🌟 Join Us for FAIRfest to Celebrate Advancements in FAIR Solutions within EOSC!	23 December 2024
16	Next Week - Join the FAIR Implementation Workshop 5 December 2024, 15:00 CET	27 November 2024
15	FAIR-IMPACT last open call, FAIRfest, FAIR implementation stories & tools: FAIR-IMPACT Newsletter is out!	21 November 2024
14	Get ready for the Synchronisation Force, discover the 45 resources in FAIR-Implementation catalogue, summer events: enjoy the FAIR-IMPACT Summer edition! 🌞	6 August 2024
13	Join the FAIR-IMPACT's Second Open Call Webinar Tomorrow 8 May 2024, 11:00 CEST	7 May 2024
12	Join us in enhancing our collective understanding of doing FAIR mapping	29 April 2024
11	FAIR-IMPACT Second Open Call for Support Apply before 31 March 2024	5 March 2024
10	🌟 16 January 2024 🌟 start the new year with sparkles! Join the FAIR-IMPACT Community event!	21 December 2023
9	A Lot Of Events Are Filling Up Our Autumn At FAIR-IMPACT! The New Series Of Workshops, The SynchForce 2023, Two Papers Published And Much More!	14 November 2023

¹¹⁴ <https://fair-impact.eu/communication-kit>

# Issue	Title issue	Distribution Date
8	The second All Hands Meeting in The Hague - Events in the Spotlight and More	6 October 2023
7	Three FAIR Implementation Workshops this August about the next FAIR-IMPACT OpenCall, Semantic Artefact Governance Workshop: our? August newsletter!	16 August 2023
6	Synchronisation Force 2023, results of the first open call, national roadshows & events: enjoy our ? July newsletter!	28 July 2023
5	Apply before 1 June 2023 for the FAIR-IMPACT open call for support Register for the webinar for potential applicants Next events & More!	11 May 2023
4	The FAIR IMPACT First Open Call Launched Welcome To The EOSC FAIR Champions New Reports, Next Events & More!	31 March 2023
3	Apply by 10 March to be one of the 12 FAIR Champions Contribute to the FAIR Implementation Framework Meet the new HLAC experts Newsletter #3	3 February 2023
2	SEASON's FAIR Greetings! FAIR-IMPACT Newsletter #2	22 December 2022
1	The Synchronisation Force is back! FAIR-IMPACT Newsletter #1	26 October 2022

Table 4: list of newsletter distributed

11.5. Video pitches & interviews

FAIR-IMPACT has produced several interviews with the coordinators of FAIR-IMPACT action lines. These videos were instrumental in sharing key project content, such as use case stories and project highlights. To improve accessibility and navigation, the videos have been organised into a thematic playlist called “Interviews” on the FAIR-IMPACT YouTube channel.

# Issue	Video Title	Video Link
1	Suzanne Dumouchel interview at the FAIR IMPACT kick off meeting on June 2022 in Amsterdam	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fvRWPPQexIo&list=PL-ASA6htb5mm-eR9Stk4rjlekpUTHNkza&index=9
2	FAIR principles applied to photon and neutron science facilities. Interview with Simon Lambert, STFC	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TOdx--Zyam8&list=PL-ASA6htb5mm-eR9Stk4rjlekpUTHNkza&index=8
3	The UK Data Archive use cases on social	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=L

	sciences. Interview with Hervé L'Hours	xTmQU7IEiA&list=PL-ASA6htb5mm-eR9Stk4rjlekpUTHNkza&index=7
4	FAIR-IMPACT contribution to Metadata and Ontologies in EOSC: interview with Clément Jonquet, INRAE	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1roM3L2XmAk&list=PL-ASA6htb5mm-eR9Stk4rjlekpUTHNkza&index=6
5	Metadata and Ontologies: the role of Ecoportal - Nicola Fiore (Lifewatch ERIC)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pZ1mirmTZFE&list=PL-ASA6htb5mm-eR9Stk4rjlekpUTHNkza&index=5
6	The Persistent Identifiers - PIDs - are a crucial building block in the FAIR principles.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wcAj5_c5RQo&list=PL-ASA6htb5mm-eR9Stk4rjlekpUTHNkza&index=4
7	Take action and start putting FAIR into practice as the main focus of WP2 - Engagement & Adoption	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gDQbh-UaqZY&list=PL-ASA6htb5mm-eR9Stk4rjlekpUTHNkza&index=3&t=13s
8	A FAIR collaboration explained by Ingrid Dillo (FAIR-IMPACT) & Tommi Suominen (FAIRCORE4EOSC)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UOeMA725Rw&list=PL-ASA6htb5mm-eR9Stk4rjlekpUTHNkza&index=2&t=12s

Table 5: List of the Interviews conducted

11.6. Podcasts

As part of its contribution to the FAIR-IMPACT project, two podcasts have been produced, offering valuable insights into key topics within the FAIR and Open Science communities.

- The first episode features Javier de la Cueva, FAIR-IMPACT Champion and legal expert,¹¹⁵ who explores the critical role of legal interoperability in implementing FAIR principles, drawing from his extensive experience in free software communities and current efforts within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). It was distributed in collaboration with the **FAIR Data Podcast series**.¹¹⁶
- The second episode brings together Gabriela Mejias (DataCite) and Wim Hugo (KNAW-DANS)¹¹⁷ to discuss the adoption of **Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)** in Europe, highlighting how international collaboration and the joint work of FAIR-IMPACT and

¹¹⁵ <https://fair-impact.eu/news/fair-data-podcast1-unlocking-fair-interoperability-navigating-legal-aspects>

¹¹⁶ <https://creators.spotify.com/pod/profile/fairdatapodcast00/episodes/Javier-de-la-Cueva-e2md7os/a-abetpfi>

¹¹⁷ <https://fair-impact.eu/news/fair-data-podcast2-future-collaboration-needs-around-pids>

FAIRCORE4EOSC are helping to define principles and best practices for PID usage within the EOSC framework.

12. KPIS

Through the project lifetime, FAIR-IMPACT created an engaged community, including representatives of the key stakeholder groups identified by the consortium, interested in knowing more about the FAIR-IMPACT activities and in learning how to exploit them for their activities. The FAIR-IMPACT consortium effectively coordinated efforts and activities in support of the dissemination of the different FAIR-IMPACT outputs towards its community, leading to the achievement in terms of engaged stakeholders as presented in the table below.

Type	Results by end project	KPI by end project
Website & knowledge hub & ZENODO		
N° sessions per month (FAIR Impact website)	4.050 views / months	3.000
ZENODO: avg. downloads per individual resource	205	300
Cascading Grants		
N° Open calls with financial support launched	3	3
N° Open calls for expert non financial support launched	3	3
In-kind expert support: Projects supported	77 teams, 72 organisations	40
Financial support: Applicants supported	128 teams, 90 organisations	40
FAIR implementation framework		
N° interactions	2	2
Press releases & Implementation Stories		
N° PR produced	2 project PR + 6 announcements about each open call	5
FAIR implementation stories	150	50
Communication Material		
N° Video pitches & podcast interviews	61	28
N° Newsletters	21	18
Social Media		
N° total of social media followers	2.626	3.000
Events & Webinars		
N° FAIR implementation workshops	21	20
N° Participants in each FAIR Implementation Workshop (average)	71	60

Type	Results by end project	KPI by end project
PID Policy Alignment Workshops (t3.3)	4	3
N° 3rd party events with active role	82	20
N° Synchronization Force Workshops	3	3
N°Participants in Synchronization Force Workshops (average number)	100	70
N° National Roadshows	14	6
N° Joint dissemination activity with FAIRCORE4EOSC	10	1

Table 6 FAIR-IMPACT KPIs

13. Conclusion

Over the 36-month lifetime, the FAIR-IMPACT project delivered a comprehensive Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation strategy that engaged diverse stakeholders and maintained continuous project visibility. The project supported over 200 teams and 150+ organisations through six open calls, while mobilising a community of more than 3600 individuals in Europe and abroad. The Synchronisation Force fostered critical dialogue within the EOSC environment, leaving as a legacy 15 actionable recommendations from targeted workshops, almost 50 deliverables and milestones that provide tangible guidelines and recommendation for implementation of the FAIR principles, that are there for immediate uptake by Task Forces and Opportunity Area Expert Groups of EOSC Association, INFRAEOSC projects, RPOs, repositories and individual researchers. On top of this, a huge amount of use cases and FAIR implementation stories demonstrated that implementing FAIR is doable, and gave examples from domain-specific communities. The project adopted a wide range of tools and channels - multimedia content, newsletters, social media, global and national events, webinars, online workshops, scientific publications, podcasts and interviews - thus ensuring widespread dissemination in all EU countries .

Ultimately, the key legacy of the project is the strengthened collaboration established throughout the mobilised community, that will continue work together to advance FAIR principles adoption for continued and long-term impact within the evolving EOSC ecosystem.

“You get better by participating in communities. You don’t get better on your own”

Beth Knazook, Digital Repository of Ireland, beneficiary of one of the FAIR-IMPACT support programme presenting at the FAIRfest, February 2025

Annex 1 - FAIR implementation stories developed

This is the list of the implementation stories, grouped by support received, indicating the scientific domain.

N	Title	Support Received
1	Prototyping the JACQ Herbarium Specimen Digital Asset metadata model - <i>Domain Natural Sciences</i>	Managing data types, schemas and vocabularies and crosswalks for FAIR researcher related metadata
2	Connecting HUN-REN ARP's schema registry with FAIR-IMPACT's Data Type Registry - <i>Domain Engineering and Technology</i>	
3	Developing a Research Data Services for the Repository "DataverseUA" of the the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine - <i>Domain Natural Sciences</i>	
4	Boosting validation and interoperability to drive FAIR principles forward at IsoArch - <i>Domain Natural Sciences</i>	
5	FAIR-IMPACT Services: Publishing FAIRer schema and vocabulary components - <i>Domain Social Sciences and Humanities</i>	
6	Developing Data Acquisition Metadata Schema for the Faculty of Economics and Administration at Masaryk University, Czech Republic - <i>Domain Social Sciences and Humanities</i>	
7	Using the FAIRCORE4EOSC's Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR) to enhance the interoperability of the University of Strasbourg's POUNT platform (Plateforme Ouverte Numérique Transdisciplinaire) - <i>Domain Agnostic</i>	
8	Testing the trustworthy and FAIR-enabling repositories prototype at the Digital Repository of Ireland - <i>Domain Social Sciences and Humanities</i>	Testing the trustworthy and FAIR-enabling repositories prototype
9	Enhancing the trustworthiness, FAIRness, and findability of University of Padua digital repositories. The case of Research Data Unipd - <i>Domain agnostic</i>	
10	Increasing trustworthiness of the Austrian NeuroCloud by providing repository-level metadata based - <i>Domain Social Sciences and Humanities</i>	
11	Turning trustworthy and FAIR-enabling e-cienciaDatos, the data repository of the Consorcio Madroño - <i>Domain Agnostic</i>	
12	FAIR and trustworthy: Advancing metadata transparency at IsoArch - <i>Domain Natural Sciences</i>	
13	Implementing a FAIR-enabling data repository attributes prototype in KU Leuven RDR - <i>Domain Agnostic</i>	

N	Title	Support Received
14	Improving the findability, interoperability, and trustworthiness of the INFRA-ART Spectral Library – a dedicated data service for the heritage science domain - <i>Domain Agnostic</i>	
15	Exposing the trustworthiness of the Research Data Repository at University College London – Challenges and opportunities - <i>Domain Engineering and Technology</i>	
16	Towards an EOSC compliant interoperability policy for the Austrian NeuroCloud - <i>Domain Social Sciences and Humanities</i>	
17	Enhancing interoperability at the Digital Repository of Ireland - <i>Domain Social Sciences and Humanities</i>	Creating EOSC compliant interoperability policies based on EOSC Interoperability Framework (IF)
18	Developing an interoperability policy roadmap for the INFRA-ART Spectral Library at the National Institute for Research and Development in Optoelectronics - <i>Domain Agnostic</i>	
19	Implementing FAIR signposting in the University of Novi Sad in-house developed eInfrastructure - <i>Domain Agnostic</i>	
20	Implementing FAIR signposting to Eurac Research geospatial data catalogue - <i>Domain Earth and environmental sciences</i>	Enabling FAIR Signposting and RO-Crate for content/metadata discovery and consumption
21	FAIR Signposting for current and future versions of the Tunisian portal for research outputs - <i>Domain Earth and environmental sciences</i>	
22	Implementing RO-Crate support for the ARP data repository platform at the Institute for Computer Science and Control - <i>Domain Agnostic</i>	
23	FAIR Signposting and RO-Crate Integration in Dataverse at KU Leuven - <i>Domain Agnostic</i>	
24	Using FAIR Signposting and RO-Crate at the German National Library of Medicine <i>Domain Life Science</i>	
25	Implementing FAIR Signposting and RO-Crate for Spanish research institutions - <i>Domain Agnostic</i>	
26	FAIR Signposting and RO Crate for the University of Oslo's Archaeological Digital Excavation Documentation - <i>Domain Social Sciences and Humanities</i>	
27	Applying FAIR Signposting and RO-Crate at NFDI4Health - <i>Domain Life Science</i>	

N	Title	Support Received
28	Navigating FAIR Waters: A Journey of Transformation for Radboud University's Data Repository - <i>Domain Agnostic</i>	FAIRness assessment challenge
29	FAIRness assessment of Generations and Gender Programme longitudinal survey dataset - <i>Domain Social Sciences and Humanities</i>	
30	F-UJI for FAIRness assessment and PhD training at Gdansk University of Technology Library - <i>Domain Agnostic</i>	
31	FAIRness assessment as a catalyst of chemistry research repository transformation in Germany - <i>Domain Agnostic</i>	
32	Making the metadata machine-readable to increase FAIRness of medical data in Poland - <i>Domain Life Science</i>	
33	FAIRness assessment of datasets and ontologies at Eurac Research - <i>Domain Earth and environmental sciences</i>	
34	FAIRness assessment of vocabularies: Insights from the British Oceanographic Data Centre team - <i>Domain Earth and environmental sciences</i>	
35	FAIRness assessment in the Life Cycle Assessment domain - <i>Domain Life Science</i>	
36	Applying the FAIR Data Maturity Model at the German Medical Data Integration Centers - <i>Domain Life Science</i>	Research Software MetaData (RSMD) guidelines
37	Promoting SearchSECO through the RSMD Guidelines - <i>Domain Agnostic</i>	
38	Implementing the Research Software MetaData (RSMD) guidelines for EcoJulia - <i>Domain Agnostic</i>	
39	Implementing the RSMD guidelines for the benefit of the battery modelling community - <i>Domain Agnostic</i>	Assessing and improving existing research software using a new extension of F-UJI"
40	Evaluating the FAIRness of Health Research Software at Leipzig University Using an Automated FAIR Assessment Tool - <i>Domain Agnostic</i>	
41	Towards greater visibility and re-use of software developed within the SeaDataNet infrastructure: the example of OCTOPUS Software - <i>Domain Agnostic</i>	
42	FAIRification of Augusta, Research Software for Gene Regulatory Networks and Boolean Models Inference - <i>Domain Life Science</i>	
43	Developing tools to support the creation of CodeMeta files - <i>Domain Agnostic</i>	

N	Title	Support Received
44	Scoop-Argo : Open-Source Software Development, Preservation, and Collaboration - <i>Domain Earth and environmental sciences</i>	
45	Improving FAIRness of ShExML and DMAOG and metadata creation workflow - <i>Domain Agnostic</i>	
46	FAIR Metrics for Research Software: Automated and Manual Testing of the FAIR Data Pipeline - <i>Domain Agnostic</i>	
47	Improving the FAIRness of a similarity search application with associated data in the life science domain - <i>Domain Life Science</i>	
48	FAIRness assessment using F-UJI for selected research software repositories in the SemTec team at ZB MED Equation - <i>Domain Life Science</i>	
49	FAIR Implementation Story of Schrödinger API: A RESTful Web Service for Solving the Multidimensional Time independent Schrödinger - <i>Domain Agnostic</i>	
50	Journey Towards FAIR Metrics for Research Software: Experiences from Simula Research Laboratory - <i>Domain Agnostic</i>	
51	Enhancing awareness and participation in FAIR data management practices at the University of Milan - <i>Domain Social Sciences and Humanities</i>	RPO Support Programme
52	Improving Radboud University's Research Data Management Policy - <i>Domain Agnostic</i>	
53	Developing a Research Data Policy for the Finnish Research Stations - <i>Domain Earth and environmental sciences</i>	
54	Promoting FAIR principles in biomedical and healthcare research centers: experience of participation in the European FAIR-IMPACT support program and its implementation through a training action plan - <i>Domain Earth and environmental sciences</i>	
55	Towards a FAIR multiplatform data observatory in the SE Bay of Biscay - <i>Domain Earth and environmental sciences</i>	
56	Developing an Open Science policy for Meise Botanic Garden (Belgium) - <i>Domain agnostic</i>	
57	Towards making the Research Analysis Identifier (RAI ID) EOSC PID policy compliant - <i>Domain Life Science</i>	PID Support Programme
58	Developing a PID Roadmap for the European Holocaust Research Infrastructure (EHRI) - <i>Domain Social Sciences and Humanities</i>	

N	Title	Support Received
59	Planning and creating a PID Policy at the Gdańsk University of Technology - finding solutions for legal and ethical considerations when working with sensitive data from technical and engineering disciplines - <i>Domain Technical and Engineering sciences</i>	
60	Assessing a PID policy for datasets Registration Service at GESIS and ZBW - <i>Domain Agnostic</i>	
61	Development of the Persistent Identifier Policy for the Lithuanian Data Archive for Social Sciences and Humanities (LiDA)	
62	Supporting PID policies through research tools/platforms - <i>Domain Agnostic</i>	
63	Developing a National PID Recommendation for Sweden and using FAIRCORE4EOSC's Compliance Assessment Toolkit to further develop the PID policy of the Swedish National Data Service - <i>Domain Agnostic</i>	

Annex 2 - Events

Contribution to third party events

N	Date	Title	Where	Activities
1	2022-11-11	EOSC Symposium 2022	Prague, Czech Republic	Joint-talk with Skills4EOSC 2 Joint Workshops with FAIRCORE4EOSC 1 FAIR-IMPACT workshop 1 Panel discussion
2	2023-03-24	RDA Plenary	Gothenburg, Sweden	1 Joint Workshop with FAIRCORE4EOSC
3	2024-11-11	RDA Plenary	San José, Costa Rica	1 FAIR-IMPACT workshop
4	2024-12-03	EUDAT Conference 2024	Karlsruhe, Germany	1 FAIR-IMPACT session
5	2025-01-12	EOSC Winter School 2025	Seville, Spain	1 FAIR-IMPACT workshop

N	Date	Title	Where	Activities
6	2025-02-17	19th International Digital Curation Conference	Den Haag, The Netherlands	1 FAIR-IMPACT workshop

FAIR Impact events related to Mappings and Semantic Artefacts

N	Date	Title	Where	N° registrations
1	2023-04-13	Why Mappings Matter and how to make them FAIR?	Online	119
2	2023-09-28	FAIR-IMPACT's Semantic Artefact Governance Workshop	Lecce, Italy	82
3	2023-11-24	Documenting mapping community practices	Online	91
4	2024-04-30	Developing a mapping process framework	Online	100

FAIR-IMPACT Workshops related to Mappings and Semantic Artefacts

N	Date	Title	Where	N° registrations
1	2023-05-25	PID best practices for complex data citation, semantic artefacts and related services	Online	67
2	2023-11-21	EOSC Compliant PID Implementations - Practical Guidelines for Implementing Best Practices	Online	84

FAIR-IMPACT Workshop on Metadata Collection and Curation for Research Software

N	Date	Title	Where	N° registrations
1	2023-05-23	Developing Guidelines for Metadata Collection and Curation for Research Software	Online	84

FAIR Implementation Workshops

N	Date	Title	N° Registrations	Cooperation with?
1	2023-11-10	Supporting FAIR adoption at the national level: Denmark	88	N/A
2	2023-11-23	Community Engagement: why it is key for Open Science and how to unleash it	77	Skills4EOSC & INOSC
3	2023-12-04	FAIR-by-Design Methodology: how to develop FAIR materials	108	Skills4EOSC
4	2024-02-01	FAIR national plan in Germany and national initiatives to support FAIR in Romania	22	NFDI & RO-NOSCI
5	2024-02-02	Engaging researchers with FAIR-ness	47	EOSC Researcher and Engagement Task Force
6	2024-02-06	Open Access publishing in FAIR action plans	43	Craft-OA EOSC
7	2024-02-27	Building FAIR skills at a national level	108	Skills4EOSC
8	2024-04-04	French Data Management Clusters	33	RDG
9	2024-05-14	Assessing national current FAIR-enabling capabilities	65	N/A
10	2024-12-25	Where do I start with FAIRification of sensitive data?	145	N/A
11	2024-07-02	Skills4EOSC Minimum Viable Skills Profiles: Implementation using FAIR Signposting	53	Skills4EOSC
12	2024-12-05	Repository Trust Resources: Pick & Mix for your Local Needs	179	N/A
13	2024-01-15	Exploring Costs and Incentives for Data Management: Perspectives, Tools, and the Role of Funders	160	N/A

N	Date	Title	N° Registrations	Cooperation with?
14	2024-03-20	Using F-UJI to Assess the FAIRness of your Data	160	N/A
15	2024-03-20	Advancing FAIR Semantic Artefact Discovery and Search: OntoPortal Federation Joint Release	78	OntoPortal
16	2025-03-24	OAIS version 3 - What does it mean for repositories?	305	N/A
17	2025-04-02	The Hungarian Research Network's (HUN-REN) Research Data Repository Platform	25	HUN-REN Data Repository Platform
18	2025-04-16	What is a 'Data Champion' and how can they support good practice in data management and sharing	183	N/A
19	2025-04-29	Meet the SoftWare Hash Identifier: Do one thing and do it well	46	N/A
20	2025-05-08	Enhancing FAIR and Trustworthy Data Repositories: Insights from the Repositories in the Western Balkan Region	91	N/A
21	2025-05-22	Measuring FAIR4RS: application of the F-UJI tool to the Ersilia Model Hub	27	N/A

FAIR-IMPACT Webinar to support the Open Calls programmes

N	Date	Title	N° registrations
1	2023-03-27	Webinar: FAIR-IMPACT Open Call for Support	126
2	2023-05-16	Webinar: FAIR-IMPACT's Virtual Clinic for potential applicants to the first Open Call	37
3	2023-08-25	FAIR Implementation Workshop - Support for National Level Initiatives	46

N	Date	Title	N° registrations
4	2023-08-28	FAIR Implementation Workshop - Support for Research Performing Organisations	72
5	2023-08-29	FAIR Implementation Workshop - Support for Repositories & Data Service Providers	70
6	2023-10-18	Workshop: FAIR-IMPACT's virtual clinic for potential applicants to the second open call for support	50
7	2024-01-31	FAIR-IMPACT's second open call for Route 2 support	64
8	2024-03-12	Webinar: FAIR-IMPACT's virtual clinic for potential applicants to the second open call for financial support	46
9	2024-05-08	FAIR-IMPACT's 2nd open call for repository support programme	29
10	2024-06-05	FAIR-IMPACT's virtual clinic for potential applicants to the 2nd open call for repository support programme	27
11	2024-06-20	FAIR-IMPACT's 2nd open call for National-Level Initiatives Webinars	16
12	2024-10-09	Webinar to introduce FAIR-IMPACT's final open call for financial support	44
13	2024-11-13	FAIR-IMPACT's virtual clinic for potential applicants to the third open call for financial support	40

Additional visibility at third party events

N	Date	Event	Location	Activity
1	2022 June	IASSIST 2022	Sweden, Gothenburg	Panel discussion
2	2022 June	CHORUS Forum	Online	Networking
3	2022 July	OntoCommons Knowledge Exchange	Online	Presentation
4	2022 July	SIGIDUS Seminar series	Online	Presentation

N	Date	Event	Location	Activity
5	2022 July	ESIP meeting 2022	USA, Pittsburgh	Presentation
6	2023 August	Meeting EOSC TF for Long-Term Data Preservation	Online	Presentation
7	2022 August	AgroHackathon 2022 FAIRness assessment	France, Montpellier	Presentation
8	2022 September	1st Workshop on Ontologies for FAIR and FAIR Ontologies (Onto4FAIR)	Austria, Vienna	Workshop
9	2022 September	EUDAT Conference 2022	Greece, Athens	Workshop
10	2022 September	EOSC Regional Event - NI4OS-Europe	Hungary, Budapest	Networking
11	2022 October	EERA Data Workshop 5: Sustainable models for FAIR and open low carbon energy research data: Business models, licensing and certification	Belgium, Brussels	Communication Materials
12	2022 October	Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration conference 2022	Online	Presentation
13	2022 October	IberGrid 2022	Portugal, Faro	Presentation
14	2022 October	Webinar on user experience with FAIR evaluation tools and services	Online	Presentation
15	2022 October	FAIRCORE4EOSC Webinar: Developing new EOSC-Core components for a FAIRer Open Science ecosystem	Online	Panel discussion
16	2022 October	Closing webinar of French project FooSIN	Online	Presentation

N	Date	Event	Location	Activity
17	2022 October	International Conference on Research Infrastructures 2022	Czech Republic, Brno	Panel discussion
18	2022 October	NFDI4Ing Conference 2022	Online	Presentation
19	2022 October	1st International Conference on FAIR Digital Objects	The Netherlands, Leiden	Panel discussion
20	2022 October	Open Science and Innovation in Ukraine	Online	Presentation
21	2022 November	EOSC National Tripartite Event Georgia	Georgia, Tbilisi	Networking
22	2022 November	Elixir BioHackathon Europe 2022	France, Paris	Presentation
23	2022 November	EOSC Symposium	Czech Republic, Prague	Workshops
24	2022 November	euroCRIS	The Netherlands, Nijmegen	Presentation
25	2022 December	e-IRG Workshop under Czech EU Presidency	Czech Republic, Prague	Panel discussion
26	2023 January	Webinar: EOSC in 2023 and RDA 10th anniversary year	Online	Presentation
27	2023 February	NISO Plus 2023 session: Communicating the value of PIDs and metadata: What's in it for me, what's in it for you?	Online	Presentation
28	2023 February	Dissemination event EU-FAR – EU Funds by Area Results	Online	Presentation
29	2023 March	e-Science Tage	Germany, Heidelberg	Presentation

N	Date	Event	Location	Activity
30	2023 March	Progressing Machine Actionable Data Management Plans in DMPRoadmap	Sweden, Gothenburg	Presentation
31	2023 March	Progressing Machine Actionable Data Management Plans in DMPRoadmap	Online	Presentation
32	2023 March	RDA Plenary	Sweden, Gothenburg	Presentation
33	2023 March	Overview about FDO/PID related Projects	Online	Presentation
34	2023 March	MD-NOSCI Inaugural Event in the Republic of Moldova	Moldavia	Presentation
35	2023 March	BMIR, Stanford University, Group meeting	USA; Standfor	Presentation
36	2023 April	FAIR Digital Objects Forum Defining FDO Collections (workshop)	Online	Presentation
37	2023 April	EGU2023	Austria, Vienna	Presentation
38	2023 May	PV2023 - Ensuring Long-Term Preservation and Adding Value to Scientific and Technical Data	Switzerland, Geneva	Presentation
39	2023 May	ELIXIR All Hands	Ireland, Dublin	Presentation
40	2023 June	H2020 OntoCommons 2nd Global Workshop	Online	Presentation
41	2023 June	DSSC Thematic Group Technology meeting #14	Online	Presentation
42	2023 June	IEA Wind Task 43 Metadata Challenge Webinar Series	Online	Presentation
43	2023 June	National Tripartite Event France	France, Montpellier	Presentation
44	2023 June	EOSC Concertation Meeting	Belgium, Brussels	Networking
45	2023 June	The Potential of Research Data: How Research	Sweden, Lund	Panel discussion

N	Date	Event	Location	Activity
		Infrastructures Provide New Opportunities and Benefits for Society		
46	2023 June	D2KAB ANR project Scientific annual day	France, Avignon	Presentation
47	2023 June	Open Science Conference	Online	Workshop
48	2023 July	Agrovoc Editorial Committee Meeting	Germany, Friesing	Presentation
49	2023 September	1st Conference on Research Data Infrastructure	Germany, Karlsruhe,	Poster
50	2023 September	63rd Jour Fixe for the German state initiative for research data management fdm.nrw	Online	Presentation
51	2023 September	FAIR-EASE 2nd Annual Meeting	Spain, Madrid	Presentation
52	2023 September	EOSC Symposium	Karlsruhe,	Workshop
53	2023 September	OpenScienceFair	Karlsruhe,	Workshop
54	2023 September	LifeWatch Semantic Academy	Italy, Lecce	Presentation
55	2023 October	Open science - news from the perspective of open access, research evaluation and FAIR data	Online	Presentation
56	2023 October	RIVM Knowledge Session: Open & FAIR developments in Europe - guest lecture with Marjan Grootveld (DANS)	The Netherlands, Bilthoven	Presentation
57	2023 October	Free University Amsterdam: Open & FAIR developments in Europe	The Netherlands, Amsterdam	Presentation
58	2023 October	GO-FAIR Agro Brazil network seminar	Online	Presentation
59	2023 October	ICRI 2022	Czech Republic, Brno	Presentation

N	Date	Event	Location	Activity
60	2023 October	ENLIGHT Workshop #3 - Health and wellbeing in a data and AI driven context: legal challenges and opportunities	Virtual	Presentation
61	2023 October	SciDataCon2023 (International Data Week)	Austria, Salzburg	Workshop
62	2023 November	DeiC Conference	Denmark, Kolding	Presentation
63	2023 November	IVOA Interop Meeting (Nov 2023)	USA, Tucson	Presentation
664	2024 January	EOSC Winter School OA2 and OA3	Enschede, Netherlands	Networking
65	2024 February	18th International Digital Curation Conference	Edinburgh, Scotland	Workshop
66	2024 February	Experiences in Implementing the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science – Online Workshop for National Commissions to Share Good Practices	Online	Presentation
67	2024 February	PARC & F-UJI Discussion	Online	Networking
68	2024 March	Workshop Open Science and Education	Online	Presentation
69	2024 March	Webinar series of the VerbundFDB metadata working group	Online	Presentation
70	2024 March	Official launch of Research Portal Denmark	Denmark	Networking
71	2024 April	EGU2024	Austria, Vienna	Poster
72	2024 May	AK FDM (Baden-Württemberg research data community)	Germany, Stuttgart	Presentation
73	2024 May	EuroCRIS2024	Austria, Vienna	Networking
74	2024 May	PhenoHarmoniS Workshop	France, Montpellier	Presentation

N	Date	Event	Location	Activity
75	2024 May	Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC) Annual Members Unconference and Networking Event	Ireland, Dublin	Presentation
76	2024 June	Open Repositories 2024	Gothenburg, Sweden	Poster
77	2024 June	PIDfest 2024	Prague, Czech Republic	Poster & Workshop
78	2024 June	D2KAB ANR project Scientific closing meeting	Hybrid	Presentation
79	2024 July	FOAM 2024: FAIR principles for Ontologies and Metadata in Knowledge Management	Netherlands, Enschede	Workshop
80	2024 July	HMC FAIR Friday	Germany	Presentation
81	2024 August	Finnish Research Service Days 2024	Finland, Vaasa	Presentation
82	2024 September	EOSC Tripartite Event France	France, Paris	Poster
83	2024 September	IPRES 024	Belgium, Ghent	Poster
84	2024 September	EGI 2024	Italy, Lecce	Exhibition booth
85	2024 October	FAIR-EASE Open Day on Open Science for Earth Systems	Italy, Naples	Presentation
86	2024 October	EOSC Symposium 2024	Germany, Berlin	Workshop
87	2024 November	Beaming Open Science Clustering Event	Serbia, NoviSad	Presentation
88	2024 November	SIMBig Conference	Peru, Ilo	Presentation
89	2024 December	EUDAT Conference 2024	Karlsruhe, Germany	Workshop
90	2024 January	EOSC Focus T3.3 workshop on Data Spaces	Vienna, Austria	Networking

N	Date	Event	Location	Activity
91	2025 January	EOSC Winter School	Spain, Seville	Networking
92	2025 February	IDCC 2025	Den Haag	Workshop